

West Bengal Assembly Election 2021: An Analysis

Onkar Singh

Global Corporate Citizenship, Accenture, Bangalore, India.

Email: os2137@caa.columbia.edu | ORCID: 0000-0002-8050-0501

ABSTRACT

West Bengal Assembly election was one of the most keenly watched assembly elections in India in 2021. One of the reasons for this interest was the unexpected rise of the Bhartiya Janata Party in a state mostly known for its contests between the Left parties, the Indian National Congress, and the All-India Trinamool Congress. The Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP) had only 3 seats in the last assembly election of 2016, whereas the ruling All India Trinamool Congress (AITC or TMC) party had 212 seats. The BJP was never a major player in the state except during the last parliamentary election (2019) when BJP bagged 18 out of the 42 parliamentary seats. The analysis presented in this paper analyzes the constituency-wise figures for each of the 294 constituencies spread over 19 districts of the state of West Bengal in India. The TMC emerged victorious with 48% of the total popular votes, while the opposition BJP got 39% of the popular votes. Also, TMC won 213 (73%) of total seats, whereas the BJP came to a distant second with 77 (26%) seats, even though it raised its stock significantly in the West Bengal Assembly from its 2016 tally of a meager 3 seats. After the West Bengal 2021 election results, Mamata Banerjee emerged as one of the main challengers of BJP at the national arena of Indian politics. This paper will benefit and help anyone interested in Indian political analysis and would also provide key insights for the political analysts and the political parties interested in a seat-by-seat deep dive. The analysis was done with the help of Microsoft Excel and R Software.

Keywords: Assembly election; Political parties; Election analysis; Vote share; India

Received: 18 July 2021

Reviewed: 30 July 2021

Accepted: 05 August 2021

Published: 20 August 2021

How to cite this paper: Singh, O. (2021). West Bengal Assembly Election 2021: An Analysis. *Journal of Policy & Governance*, 01(01), 69-121. <https://doi.org/10.33002/jpg010107>

Copyright © 2021 by author(s). This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Open Access

1. INTRODUCTION

West Bengal¹ Assembly election was one of the most keenly watched assembly elections in India in 2021. One of the reasons for this interest was the unexpected rise of the Bhartiya Janata Party² in a state mostly known for its contests between the Left³ parties, the Indian National Congress⁴, and the All-India Trinamool Congress⁵. The Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP) had only 3 seats in the last assembly election of 2016, whereas the ruling All India Trinamool Congress (AITC or TMC) party had 212 seats. The BJP was never a major player in the state except during the last parliamentary election (2019) when BJP bagged 18 out of the 42 parliamentary seats. This raised the optimism in the BJP camp. The party put all its political might in the West Bengal Legislative Assembly election, which was concluded in May 2021, where it was pitted against the ruling TMC led by its supremo Mamata Banerjee. The stakes were so high that BJP made some of its central ministers resign to contest the assembly elections to bolster the party's prospects in the state, traditionally considered home to the non-BJP political forces.

This was coupled with the high decibel election campaign led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi along with the Home Minister Amit Shah and BJP President J.P. Nadda. On the other hand, the two-time chief minister of West Bengal, Mamata Banerjee, led the incumbent party from the front and ran a highly successful campaign leading to her party's victory in the assembly election. This marked the beginning of the third term of the TMC government in the state. The opinion and exit polls were equally divided some predicted edge to the ruling TMC while others giving a slight edge to the BJP. However, the final results, announced on 2nd May 2021, put all speculations to rest with TMC winning 213 seats, whereas BJP managed to win only 77 seats.

The analysis presented in this paper attempts to analyze the constituency-wise figures for each of the 294 constituencies spread over 19 districts of the state of West Bengal in India. This paper will benefit and help anyone interested in Indian political analysis and would also provide key insights for the political analysts and the political parties interested in a seat-by-seat deep dive. The study conducted to prepare this paper aims at synthesizing the political data using visualization for a better understanding of the election results. This would also be helpful for political analysts, political and social scientists, and political parties to further analyze the election results at a granular level. The future scope of this study would entail a demographic extrapolation on

Figure 1: Map of West Bengal Districts

¹ West Bengal is eastern state of India. <https://wb.gov.in/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/West_Bengal

² Presently the largest political party, which is also ruling in the centre (Union of India). <https://www.bjp.org/>

³ Refers to the Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPM) which rule the state of West Bengal for more than three decades [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Communist_Party_of_India_\(Marxist\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Communist_Party_of_India_(Marxist))

⁴ The oldest political of India having ruled the country for longest period. <https://www.inc.in/>

⁵ <https://aitcofficial.org/>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/All_India_Trinamool_Congress

the election results to understand various social economic and political contexts that determine the election outcomes in India.

2. METHODOLOGY

The data for the analysis conducted under this study was obtained from the Election Commission of India portal⁶ and Trivedi Center for Political Data⁷ at the Ashoka University, India. The analysis was done with the help of Microsoft Excel and R Software and its ggplot2 package for Visualization. The various reports and publications were used as a secondary source in the process of this analysis. The analysis covers each of 19 districts of the West Bengal state represented in figure 1 and provides with election results for each of the 294 assembly constituencies in West Bengal.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section and the subsequent sections provide the details of political parties, which participated in the West Bengal election, key election results such as by number and percentage of seats, regional and gender distribution of winning candidates per party, and then follows with a district-wise summary of election outcomes and delves deeper into the election results of all seats in each district of the state of West Bengal.

3.1 Total Number of Political Parties in the Fray

As mentioned in table 1, a large number of independent candidates (611) and a total of 58 political parties took part in the West Bengal assembly election 2021. The main parties include Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP), All India Trinamool Congress (AITC/TMC), Communist Party of India Marxist (CPIM), and Indian National Congress (INC/Congress). The BJP, TMC, CPIM, and Congress contested 291, 288, 138, and 91 seats, respectively (Figure 2).

Table 1: Political parties and number of seats contested

S.No.	Political Party	No. of Contested Seats
1.	Independents (IND)	611
2.	Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP)	291
3.	All India Trinamool Congress (AITC)	288
4.	Socialist Unity Centre of India (Communist) [SUCI]	188
5.	Bahujan Samaj Party (BSP)	162
6.	Communist Party of India (Marxist)(CPM)	138
7.	Indian National Congress (INC)	91
8.	Bahujan Mukti Party (BMP)	45
9.	Amra Bangalee (AB)	40
10.	Indian Secular Front (ISF/RSSCMJP)	32
11.	All India Forward Bloc (AIFB)	21
12.	Janata Dal (United) [JD(U)]	16
13.	Kamatapur People's Party (United)	15
14.	Communist Party of India (Marxist–Leninist) Liberation [CPI(ML)(L)]	12
15.	Purvanchal Mahapanchayat (PM)	12
16.	Communist Party of India (CPI)	10
17.	Lok Janshakti Party (LJP)	10
18.	Revolutionary Socialist Party (RSP)	10
19.	Bhartiya Nyay-Adhikar Raksha Party (BNARP)	8
20.	Justice and Development Party (JDP)	7
21.	Party for Democratic Socialism (PDS)	7

⁶ <https://eci.gov.in/>

⁷ <https://tcpd.ashoka.edu.in/>

S.No.	Political Party	No. of Contested Seats
22.	All India Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen (AIMIM)	6
23.	United Socialist Party (USP)	6
24.	Bahujan Maha Party (BMP)	5
25.	Indian Unity Centre (IUC)	5
26.	Republican Party of India (A) (RPI-A)	5
27.	Ambedkarite Party of India (API)	4
28.	Indian Union Muslim League (IUML)	4
29.	Jan Sangh Party (JSP)	4
30.	National Republic Party of India (NRPI)	4
31.	Republican Party of India (Athawale) (RPI-A)	4
32.	Social Democratic Party of India (SDPI)	4
33.	Socialist Party (India) (SPI)	4
34.	Welfare Party of India (WPI)	4
35.	Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) Red Star	3
36.	Democratic Socialist Party of India (DSPI)	3
37.	Hindustani Awam Morcha (HAM)	3
38.	Humanity Universal Motion Party (HUMP)	3
39.	National People's Party (NPP)	3
40.	Akhil Bharat Hindu Mahasabha (ABHM)	2
41.	All India Minorities Front (AIMF)	2
42.	Bhartiya Momin Front (BMF)	2
43.	Bhartiya Tribal Party (BTP)	2
44.	Guru Chand Mukti Morcha (GCMM)	2
45.	Mulnibasi Party of India (MPI)	2
46.	Right to Recall Party (RRP)	2
47.	West Bengal Socialist Party (WBSP)	2
48.	All Jharkhand Students Union (AJSUP)	1
49.	Bharateeya Manavadhikar Party (BMP)	1
50.	Jamat-E-Seratul Mustakim (JSM)	1
51.	Lok Samya Party (LSP)	1
52.	New Democratic Party of India (NDPI)	1
53.	Paradise Party (PP)	1
54.	Progressive People's Party (PPP)	1
55.	Rashtravadi Janata Party (RJP)	1
56.	Revolutionary Socialist Party of India (Marxist) (RSPI-M)	1
57.	Sajag Samaj Party (SSP)	1
58.	Samajwadi Jan Parishad (SJP)	1
59.	Vikas India Party (VIP)	1

3.2 Main Political Parties by Number of Seats Contested

Both TMC and BJP contested almost all of the seats, whereas other main parties in the state like CPM and Congress, had an alliance with Indian Secular Front⁸ (ISF), a newly formed party led by Abbas Siddiqui, as mentioned in table 1.

⁸ ISF fought the election on the Rashtriya Secular Majlis Party (RSMP) of Bihar which has the 'envelope' symbol. <http://www.millenniumpost.in/kolkata/isf-to-fight-polls-on-borrowed-symbol-434695>

Figure 2: Main Political parties by number of seats contested

3.3 Total Number of Repeat vs. New Candidates

In figure 3, it is depicted that a larger number of repeat candidates were fielded by the TMC, because it had the largest number of members of legislative assembly (MLAs) in the outgoing assembly, and it is not common that parties replace their seating candidates. The BJP fielded the largest number of new candidates. Since all other political parties had fewer MLAs in the assembly, they likely bet on the newer candidates than those who lost the election on their ticket last time.

Figure 3: Total number of repeat vs new candidates

3.4 Total Number of Votes Secured by Each Political Party

As shown in figure 4 below, while the ruling party TMC bagged 28.6 million votes, the BJP got 22.7 million votes. The difference in votes between the two main parties is of 5.9 million votes. CPM bagged 2.8 million votes, whereas the Congress could manage to get over 1.7 million votes.

Figure 4: Total number of votes secured by each political party

3.5 Total Percentage of Votes and the Total Number of Seats won by Parties

The analysis in figure 5 indicates that TMC emerged victorious with 48% of the total popular votes, while the opposition BJP got 39% of the popular votes. The CPM managed to win 5% of the votes followed by the Congress and Independents with 3% and 2% of the popular votes, respectively. This shows that the contest was highly polarized and bipolar between the incumbent Trinamool Congress (AITC) and

Figure 5 (left): Total percentage of votes secured by each political party

Figure 6 (right): Total number of seats secured by each political party

the opposition Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP). As indicated in figure 6 below, TMC won 213 (73% of total seats), whereas the BJP came to a distant second with 77 (26%) seats, even though it raised its stock significantly in the West Bengal Assembly from its 2016 tally of a meager 3 seats.

3.6 Total Number of Seats Secured by Each Political Party Per Region

As per figure 7 below, TMC won the largest proportions of seats in the Presidency (TMC: 111 vs. BJP: 16) and Burdwan (TMC: 79 vs. BJP: 31) divisions whereas BJP emerged as a dominant force in the Jalpaiguri division (BJP 30 vs. TMC 23).

Number of seats won by parties in each region
2021 assembly election

Figure 7: Total number of seats secured by each political party per region

3.7 Seats by Constituency Type

As per the figure 8 below, TMC won 82% of the General (or non-reserved) (168 out of 206) seats, and it won 53% (36 out of 68) of the SC and 56% of the ST (9 out of 16) reserved seats.⁹ TMC had done

Figure 8: Winner by constituency type

⁹ Reservation is a system of affirmative action in India that provides historically disadvantaged groups representation in education, employment and politics. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reservation_in_India

better electorally in General seats compared to SC and ST reserved seats. BJP won 18% of the total General or non-reserved (18 out of 206) seats and 47% of the SC (32 out of 68) and 44% of the ST (7 out of 16) reserved seats. The BJP had done better electorally in SC and ST seats compared to the General seats.

3.8 Seats with a Victory Margin of 5000 or Below

The total number of candidates who won by a margin of 5000 or less was 35 or around 12% of the total assembly seats. Out of the total 35, 63% or 22 were won by BJP and 37% or 13 were won by TMC. This indicates that more candidates from BJP won by a lower margin than TMC.

Figure 9: Winner by a margin of 5000 or less

3.9 Constituencies with Lower Voter Turnout

As depicted in figure 10 below, there were 5 constituencies with a turnout of 60% and below; in all these five constituencies the winning candidates were from the ruling TMC. However, since the seats with lower turnouts were just 5, this could just be a mere coincidence or some underlying factors that need to be further investigated if lower voter turnout favored one party over another in this state election.

Figure 10: Constituencies with lower voter turnout

3.10 Constituencies with Higher Voter Turnout

As per the figure 11 below, there were 10 constituencies with a turnout of 85 percent and above, and in these 10 constituencies, 7 were won by TMC, 2 by BJP, and 1 by Independents. Higher or lower voter turnout seems to be benefiting TMC. However, this could be a coincidental outcome as well, given TMC has a higher number of seats across the state when compared to BJP and these higher or lower turnout constituencies could be a reflection of the results across the state. This is something that needs to be investigated further.

Figure 11: Constituencies with higher voter turnout

3.11 The Chief Minister's Constituency

The Chief Minister Mamata Banerjee left her traditional safe seat and challenged her one-time confidante turned rival, Suwendu Adhikari, at his home turf in Nandigram. This contest was fierce and very close in which Suvendhu Adhikari of the BJP emerged victorious with a narrow margin of 1,956. Mamata Banerjee lost her seat, but her party, TMC, secured two-thirds of the majority in a fiercely fought West Bengal election. Eventually, she was elected Chief Minister of West Bengal for a straight third term.

Nandigram where Chief Minister Mamata Banerjee lost to Suvedhu Adhikari in a very close fight

Figure 12: The Chief Minister’s Constituency

3.12 The Gender Split of Winners by Party

Mamata Banerjee is the first woman Chief Minister of West Bengal and today is the most prominent leader of not only Bengal but also in India. Let us look at the gender splits of MLAs in her party versus the opposition BJP. As per the figure 13 below, out of the total seats won by TMC, the seats won by women were 33 or 15.5% of the total seats of 213, whereas for the BJP it was 7 seats or 9% of the total seats of 77. The proportion of women who got elected as members of the legislative assembly (MLAs) on TMC tickets is higher than that of the BJP.

Gender distribution of seats won

Figure 13: The gender split of winners by party

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS: DISTRICT-WISE

4.1 Results Summary Per District: Total number of seats secured by each political party by district

As illustrated in table 2 and figure 14 below, out of the total 19 districts, TMC bagged more seats than BJP in 12 districts (Bardhaman, Birbhum, Hooghly, Howrah, Kolkata Corporation, Maldah, Murshidabad, North 24 Parganas, Paschim Medinipur, Purba Medinipur, South 24 Parganas, and Uttar Dinajpur), whereas BJP had a bigger share of seats in only 6 districts (Bankura, Cooch Behar, Darjeeling, Jalpaiguri, Nadia, and Purulia). BJP did not win any seat in Howrah (16 seats), Kolkata Corporation (11 seats), and South 24 Parganas (30 seats) districts, whereas TMC did not win any seat in Darjeeling (6 seats).

Table 2: Total number of seats secured by each political party by district

S.No.	District Name	Party	Total Number of Seats
1.	Bankura	BJP	8
2.	Bankura	AITC	4
3.	Bardhaman	AITC	22
4.	Bardhaman	BJP	3
5.	Birbhum	AITC	10
6.	Birbhum	BJP	1
7.	Cooch Behar	BJP	7
8.	Cooch Behar	AITC	2
9.	Dakshin Dinajpur	AITC	3
10.	Dakshin Dinajpur	BJP	3
11.	Darjeeling	BJP	5
12.	Darjeeling	IND	1
13.	Hooghly	AITC	14
14.	Hooghly	BJP	4
15.	Howrah	AITC	16
16.	Jalpaiguri	BJP	9
17.	Jalpaiguri	AITC	3
18.	Kolkata Corporation	AITC	11
19.	Maldah	AITC	8
20.	Maldah	BJP	4
21.	Murshidabad	AITC	18
22.	Murshidabad	BJP	2
23.	Nadia	BJP	9
24.	Nadia	AITC	8
25.	North 24 Parganas	AITC	28
26.	North 24 Parganas	BJP	5
27.	Paschim Medinipur	AITC	17
28.	Paschim Medinipur	BJP	2
29.	Purba Medinipur	AITC	9
30.	Purba Medinipur	BJP	7
31.	Purulia	BJP	6
32.	Purulia	AITC	3
33.	South 24 Parganas	AITC	30
34.	South 24 Parganas	RSSCMJP	1
35.	Uttar Dinajpur	AITC	7
36.	Uttar Dinajpur	BJP	2

Figure 14: Total number of seats secured by each political party by district

District-wise analysis of seats earned by each political party has been given below.

4.2 Bankura District

In accordance with the analysis in figure 15 below and Annex 1, the district of Bankura has a total of 12 legislative constituencies. The district has 6 reserved constituencies out of which 4 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes¹⁰ (SC) community and 2 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Tribes¹¹ (ST) community. Seats reserved for SC include Saltora, Katulpur, Indus and Sonamukhi, and the seats reserved for ST include Ranibundh, and Raipur.

Out of the total 12 seats in the Bankura district, the largest number of seats i.e., 8 were won by the BJP while the AITC won 4 seats. The seats won by BJP were Saltora, Chhatna, Bankura, Onda, Bishnupur, Katulpur, Indus and Sonamukhi, and the seats won by AITC include Ranibundh, Raipur, Taldangra and Barjora.

Out of the total polled votes of 2,470,633, BJP secured a total of 1,119,399 (45%) votes, while the AITC secured 1,092,741 (44%) votes. The CPM with a vote share of 110,909 (4%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth position after securing 47,335 (2%) of the total votes in the district.

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scheduled_Castes_and_Scheduled_Tribes

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scheduled_Castes_and_Scheduled_Tribes

Bankura District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 15: Bankura District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.3. Bardhaman District

As the analysis in figure 16 below and Annex 2, district of Bardhaman has a total of 25 legislative constituencies. The district has 7 reserved constituencies, and all 7 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC include Khandaghosh, Raina, Jamalpur, Kalna, Bardhaman Uttar, Ausgram and Galsi.

Out of the total 25 seats in the Bardhaman district, the largest number of seats i.e., 22 were won by the AITC, while the BJP won 3 seats. The seats won by AITC were Khandaghosh, Bardhaman Dakshin, Raina, Jamalpur, Monteswar, Kalna, Memari, Bardhaman Uttar, Bhatar, Purbasthali Dakshin, Purbasthali Uttar, Katwa, Ketugram, Mangalkot, Ausgram, Galsi, Pandabeswar, Durgapur Purba, Raniganj, Jamuria, Asansol Uttar and Barbani, and the seats won by BJP were Durgapur Paschim, Asansol Dakshin and Kulti.

Out of total polled votes of 5,044,003, AITC secured a total of 2,382,485 (47%) votes, while the BJP secured 2,062,687 (41%) votes. The CPM with a vote share of 404,042 (8%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth position after securing 60,824 (1%) of the total votes in the district.

BARDHAMAN District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 16: Bardhaman District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.4. Birbhum District

The figure 17 below and Annex 3 indicate that the district of Birbhum has 11 legislative constituencies. The district has 3 reserved constituencies, and all 3 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC include Dubrajpur, Nanoor and Sainthia.

From total 11 seats in the Birbhum district, the largest number of seats i.e., 10 were won by the AITC, while the BJP won only 1 seat. The seats won by AITC were Suri, Bolpur, Nanoor, Labhpur, Sainthia, Mayureswar, Rampurhat, Hansan, Nalhati and Murarai, and the seat won by BJP was Dubrajpur.

Of total polled votes of 2,348,347, AITC secured 1,223,569 (52%) votes, while the BJP secured 931,633 (40%) of the total votes. The INC with a vote share of 65,369 (3%) was on third place, while the CPM was on the fourth position after securing 41,433 (2%) of the total votes in the district.

BIRBHUM District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 17: Birbhum District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.5. Cooch Behar District

The analysis presented in figure 18 below and Annex 4 highlights that the district of Cooch Behar has a total of 9 legislative constituencies. The district consists of 5 reserved constituencies and all 5 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. The seats reserved for SC include Mekliganj, Mathabhanga, Cooch Behar Uttar, Sitalkuchi and Sitai.

From total 9 seats in Cooch Behar district, the largest number of seats, i.e. 7, were won by the BJP, while the AITC won 2 seats. The seats won by BJP were Mathabhanga, Cooch Behar Uttar, Cooch Behar Dakshin, Sitalkuchi, Dinahata, Natabari and Tufanganj, and the seats won by AITC were Mekliganj and Sitai.

Out of the total polled votes of 1,991,218, the BJP secured a total of 984,977 (49%) votes, while the AITC secured 891,584 (45%) of the votes. The AIFB with a vote share of 34,643 (2%) was on third place, while the CPM was on the fourth position after securing 26,277 (1%) of the total votes in the district.

COOCH BEHAR District: First three candidates in each seat
 Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 18: Cooch Bihar District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.6. Dakshin Dinajpur District

The analysis depicted in figure 19 below and Annex 5 tells that the district of Dakshin Dinajpur has a total of 6 legislative constituencies. The district comprises 3 reserved constituencies out of which 2 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community, whereas 1 seat is reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC community include Kushmandi and Gangarampur, and the seat reserved for ST includes Tapan.

Viewing the results, out of the total 6 seats in the Dakshin Dinajpur district, 3 seats each were won by the AITC and the BJP, respectively. The seats won by AITC were Kushmandi, Kumarganj and Harirampur, and the seats won by BJP include Balurghat, Tapan and Gangarampur.

Coming to the total polled votes of 1,061,300, AITC secured a total of 501,418 (47%) votes, while the BJP secured 456,473 (43%) of the votes. The RSP with a vote share of 40,812 (4%) was on third place, while the CPM was on the fourth position having secured 24,717 (2%) of the total votes in the district.

DAKSHIN DINAJPUR District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 19: Dakshin Dinajpur District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.7. Darjeeling District

Figure 20 below and Annex 6 reflect that the district of Darjeeling bears a total of 6 legislative constituencies. The district has 2 reserved constituencies out of which 1 seat is reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community, whereas 1 seat is reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC include Matigara-Naxalbari, and the seat reserved for ST includes Phansidewa.

DARJEELING District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 20: Darjeeling District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

In Darjeeling district, the largest number of seats, i.e. 5, out of total 6, were won by the BJP, while the Independent candidate won 1 seat. The seats won by BJP were Darjeeling, Kurseong, Matigara-Naxalbari, Siliguri and Phansidewa, and the seat won by the Independent candidate was Kalimpong.

Looking at the vote distribution, BJP secured a total of 531,524 (48%) votes from total polled votes of 1,110,136, while the Independents secured 290,173 (26%) of the votes. The AITC with a vote share of 200,661 (18%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth position with a share of 37,590 (3%).

4.8. Hooghly District

According to the analysis portrayed in figure 21 below and Annex 7, the district of Hooghly comprises a total of 18 legislative constituencies. The district has 4 reserved constituencies, and all 4 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC include Balagarh, Dhanekhali, Arambag and Goghat.

From total 18 seats in the Hooghly district, the largest number of seats, i.e. 14, were won by the AITC, while 4 seats were won by the BJP. The seats won by AITC were Uttarpara, Sreerampur, Champdani, Singur, Chandannagore, Chunchura, Balagarh, Pandua, Saptagram, Chanditala, Jangipara, Haripal, Dhanekhali and Tarakeswar, and the seats won by BJP were Pursurah, Arambag, Goghat and Khanakul.

Out of the total polled votes of 3,778,058, AITC secured a total of 1,805,779 (48%) votes while the BJP secured 1,525,889 (40%) of the votes. The CPM with a vote share of 234,397 (6%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth position having secured 67,866 (2%) of the total votes in the district.

HOOGHLY District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 21: Hooghly District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.9. Howrah District

With regard to the analysis given in figure 22 below and Annex 8, the district of Howrah possesses a total of 16 legislative constituencies. The district comprises 2 reserved constituencies and both the seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC are Sankrail and Uluberia Uttar.

Out of the total 16 seats in the Howrah district, all seats, i.e. 16, were won by the AITC. The seats won by AITC were Bally, Howrah Uttar, Howrah Madhya, Shibpur, Howrah Dakshin, Sankrail, Panchla, Uluberia Purba, Uluberia Uttar, Uluberia Dakshin, Shyampur, Bagnan, Amta, Udaynarayanpur, Jagatballavpur and Domjur.

What was the distribution of polled votes of 3,176,015? The AITC secured a total of 1,613,916 (51%) votes, while the BJP secured 1,159,043 (36%) of the votes. The CPM with a vote share of 148,219 (5%) remained on third place, while the RSSCMJP came on to the fourth position with the vote share of 91,396 (3%) in the district.

HOWRAH District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 22: Howrah District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.10. Jalpaiguri District

The analysis in figure 23 below and Annex 9 reveals that the district of Jalpaiguri has a total of 12 legislative constituencies. The district has 10 reserved constituencies out of which 5 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community and 5 seats reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC are Falakata, Dhupguri, Maynaguri, Jalpaiguri and Rajganj, whereas the seats reserved for ST include Kumargram, Kalchini, Madarihata, Mal and Nagrakata.

Of the total 12 seats in the Jalpaiguri district, the largest number of seats, i.e. 9, were won by the BJP, while the AITC won 3 seats. The seats won by BJP were Kumargram, Kalchini, Alipurduars, Falakata, Madarihat, Dhupguri, Maynaguri, Dabgram-Phulbari and Nagrakata, and the seats won by AITC were Jalpaiguri, Rajganj and Mal.

Analysis of the total polled votes of 2,553,048 suggests that BJP secured a total of 1,226,127 (48%) votes, while the AITC secured 1,096,150 (43%) of the votes. The CPM having a vote share of 64,914 (3%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth place after obtaining 56,962 (2%) of the total votes in the district.

JALPAIGURI District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 23: Jalpaiguri District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.11. Kolkata Corporation District

As per the analysis in figure 24 below and Annex 10, the district of Kolkata Corporation comprises a total of 11 legislative constituencies. The district has no reserved constituency.

From total 11 seats in the Kolkata Corporation district, all seats, i.e. 11, were won by the AITC. The seats won by AITC were Kolkata Port, Bhabanipur, Rashbehari, Ballygunge, Chowrangee, Entally, Belehata, Jorasanko, Shyampukur, Maniktala and Kashipur-Belgachia.

Break up of total polled votes of 1,269,450 indicates that AITC secured a total of 787,308 (62%) votes, while the BJP secured 365,982 (29%) of the votes. The INC having a vote share of 40,150 (3%) reached on third place, while the CPM was on the fourth position after securing 33,142 (3%) of the total votes in the district.

KOLKATA CORPORATION District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 24: Kolkata Corporation District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.12. Maldah District

The analysis in figure 25 below and Annex 11 shows that the district of Maldah has a total of 12 legislative constituencies. The district has 3 reserved constituencies out of which 2 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community and 1 seat reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC include Gazole and Maldaha and the seat reserved for ST includes Habibpur.

The results of total 12 seats in the Maldah district indicate that the largest number of seats, i.e. 8, were won by the AITC with the BJP having won 4 seats. The seats won by AITC were Chanchal, Harischandrapur, Malatipur, Ratua, Manickchak, Mothabari, Sujapur and Baishnab Nagar, while the seats won by BJP were Habibpur, Gazole, Maldaha and Englishbazar.

Out of the total polled votes of 2,412,438, AITC attained a total of 1,277,474 (53%) votes, while the BJP secured 791,356 (33%) of the votes. The INC with a vote share of 211,488 (9%) came on third place, with the CPM at the fourth place having secured 38,708 (2%) in the total votes in the district.

MALDAH District: First three candidates in each seat
 Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 25: Maldah District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.13. Murshidabad District

As per the analysis shown in figure 26 below and Annex 12, the district of Murshidabad consists of a total of 20 legislative constituencies. The district has 3 reserved constituencies, and all 3 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. The seats reserved for SC include Nabagram, Khargram and Burwan.

From the total 20 seats in the Murshidabad district, the largest number of seats, i.e. 18, were secured by the AITC, with the BJP securing 2 seats. The seats won by AITC were Farakka, Suti, Raghunathganj, Sagardighi, Lalgola, Bhagabangola, Raninagar, Nabagram, Khargram, Burwan, Kandi, Bharatpur, Rejinagar, Beldanga, Hariharpara, Naoda, Domkal and Jalangi. The seats won by BJP were Murshidabad and Baharampur.

Seeing the distribution of total polled votes of 4,029,623, AITC had secured a total of 2,174,705 (54%) votes, while the BJP got 967,637 (24%) of the votes. The INC received 557,285 (14%) reaching the third place, and the CPM came on the fourth position having secured 211,922 (5%) of the total votes during the election.

MURSHIDABAD District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 26: Murshidabad District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.14. Nadia District

Data in figure 27 below and Annex 13 reveals that the district of Nadia has a total of 17 legislative constituencies. The district comprises 5 reserved constituencies and all 5 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC include Krishnaganj, Ranaghat Uttar Purba, Ranaghat Dakshin, Kalyani and Haringhata.

The largest number of seats (i.e., 9 out of the total 17 seats) were won by the BJP, while the AITC got 8 seats. The seats won by BJP were Krishnaganj Uttar, Santipur, Ranaghat Uttar Paschim, Krishnaganj, Ranaghat Uttar Purba, Ranaghat Dakshin, Chakdaha, Kalyani and Haringhata. On the other hand, the seats won by AITC were Karimpur, Tehatta, Palashipara, Kaliganj, Nakashipara, Chapra, Nabadwip and Krishnaganj Dakshin.

AITC secured a total of 1,611,050 (44%) votes out of total polled votes of 3,625,258, while the BJP secured 1,590,147 (44%) of the votes. The CPM with a vote share of 208,699 (6%) was on third place, while the Independents were on the fourth position after securing 99,485 (3%) of the total votes.

NADIA District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 27: Nadia District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.15. North 24 Parganas

As per the analysis given in figure 28 below and Annex 14, the district of North 24 Parganas is divided into total of 33 legislative constituencies. The district has 8 reserved constituencies out of which 7 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community and 1 seat reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC include Bagdah, Bongaon Uttar, Bongaon Dakshin, Gaighata, Swarupnagar, Minakhan and Hingalganj, whereas the seat reserved for ST includes Sandeshkhali.

Total 33 seats in the North 24 Parganas district were analyzed. The largest number of seats, i.e. 28, were secured by the AITC, while the BJP got 5 seats. The seats won by AITC were Swarupnagar, Baduria, Habra, Ashoknagar, Amdanga, Bijpur, Naihati, Jagatdal, Noapara, Barrackpur, Khardaha, Dum Dum Uttar, Panihati, Kamarhati, Baranagar, Dum Dum, Rajarhat New Town, Bidhannagar, Rajarhat Gopalpur, Madhyamgram, Barasat, Deganga, Haroa, Minakhan, Sandeshkhali, Basirhat Dakshin, Basirhat Uttar and Hingalganj. On the other side, the seats secured by BJP were Bagdah, Bongaon Uttar, Bongaon Dakshin, Gaighata and Bhatpara.

The total polled votes of 6,380,727 were analyzed. The AITC secured a total of 3,131,141 (49%) votes, whereas the BJP secured 2,217,198 (35%) of the votes. The CPM having 368,123 (6%) votes was on third place, with the RSSCMJP on the fourth position after securing 322,688 (5%) of the total votes.

NORTH 24 PARGANAS District: First three candidates in each seat
 Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 28: North 24 Parganas: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.16. Paschim Medinipur District

In accordance with the data shown in figure 29 below and Annex 15, the district of Paschim Medinipur has a total of 19 legislative constituencies. The district has 6 reserved constituencies out of which 3 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community and another 3 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC include Ghatal, Chandrakona and Keshpur, and the seats reserved for ST include Nayagram, Keshiary and Binpur.

Of 19 seats in the Paschim Medinipur district, the largest number of seats (i.e., 17) were occupied by the AITC, with the BJP secured 2 seats. The seats won by AITC were Dantan, Nayagram, Gopiballavpur, Jhargram, Keshiary, Narayangarh, Sabang, Pingla, Kharagpur, Debra, Daspur, Chandrakona, Garbeta, Salboni, Keshpur, Medinipur and Binpur. Likewise, the seats won by BJP were Kharagpur Sadar and Ghatal.

From the total polled votes of 4,028,773, AITC secured a total of 2,023,763 (50%) votes with the BJP having secured 1,695,443 (42%) votes. The CPM having vote share of 168,713 (4%) was on third place, while the INC was on the fourth place with 35,337 (1%) of the total votes in the district.

PASCHIM MEDINIPUR District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 29: Paschim Medinipur: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.17. Purba Medinipur District

As per the analysis contained in the figure 30 below and Annex 16, the district of Purba Medinipur has a total of 16 legislative constituencies. The district comprises 2 reserved constituencies and both the seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. Seats reserved for SC include Haldia and Khejuri.

Out of the total 16 seats in the Purba Medinipur district, the largest number of seats (i.e. 9) were won by the AITC while the BJP won 7 seats. The seats secured by AITC were Tamluk, Panskura Purba, Panskura Paschim, Nandakumar, Mahisadal, Chandipur, Patashpur, Ramnagar and Egra. BJP won the seats of Moyna, Haldia, Nandigram, Kanthi Uttar, Bhagabanpur, Khejuri and Kanthi Dakshin.

The distribution of polled votes of 3,519,791 shows that BJP secured a total of 1,660,061 (47%) votes while the AITC secured 1,658,308 (47%) of the votes. On the third position was the CPM having a vote share of 93,358 (3%), while the CPI was at the fourth position after securing 42,487 (1%) in the total votes in the district.

PURBA MEDINIPUR District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 30: Purba Medinipur: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.18. Purulia District

As per the analysis depicted in the figure 31 below and Annex 17 data, the district of Purulia comprises a total of 9 legislative constituencies, from which 4 are reserved constituencies. Out of those 4, 2 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community, whereas 2 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community. The seats reserved for SC include Para and Raghunathpur, and the seats reserved for ST include Bandwan and Manbazar.

Out of the 9 seats in the Purulia district, the largest number of seats (i.e., 6) were received by the BJP, while the AITC got 3 seats. The seats won by BJP were Balarampur, Joypur, Purulia, Kashipur, Para and Raghunathpur, and the seats won by AITC include Bandwan, Baghmundi and Manbazar.

Of the total polled votes of 1,847,059, the AITC obtained a total of 723,576 (39%) votes, with the BJP securing 711,977 (39%) votes. The INC came on third position with a vote share of 147,117 (8%), when the CPM was on the fourth position with 78,399 (4%) votes.

PURULIA District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 31: Purulia District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.19. South 24 Parganas District

According to the data in figure 32 below and Annex 18, the district of South 24 Parganas comprises a total of 31 legislative constituencies, from which 9 are reserved constituencies, and all 9 seats are reserved for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. The seats reserved for SC include Gosaba, Basanti, Kultali, Mandirbazar, Jaqynagar, Baruipur Purba, Canning Paschim, Magrahat Purba and Bishnupur (SC).

Out of the total 31 seats in the South 24 Parganas district, the largest number of seats (i.e. 30) were obtained by the AITC, while the RSSCMJP got only 1 seat. The seats won by AITC were Gosaba, Basanti, Kultali, Patharpratima, Kakdwip, Sagar, Kulpi, Raidighi, Mandirbazar, Jaqynagar, Baruipur Purba, Canning Paschim, Canning Purba, Baruipur Paschim, Magrahat Purba, Magrahat Paschim, Diamond Harbour, Falta, Satgachia, Bishnupur (SC), Sonarpur Dakshin, Kasba, Jadavpur, Sonarpur Uttar, Tollygunj, Behala Purba, Behala Paschim, Maheshtala, Budge Budge and Metiaburuz. The seats secured by RSSCMJP included Bhangore.

From total polled votes of 6,734,075, AITC secured a total of 3,523,407 (52%) votes, while the BJP secured 2,142,477 (32%) of the votes. The CPM with a vote share of 508,632 (8%) was on third place, while the RSSCMJP was on the fourth position with 281,963 (4%) votes in the district.

SOUTH 24 PARGANAS District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 32: South 24 Parganas District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4.20. Uttar Dinajpur District

Figure 33 below and Annex 19 demonstrate that the district of Uttar Dinajpur has a total of 9 legislative constituencies, with 2 reserved constituencies for the Scheduled Castes (SC) community. These seats reserved for SC include Hemtabad and Kaliaganj.

Who secured what out of the total 9 seats in the Uttar Dinajpur district? The largest number of seats (i.e. 7) went to AITC, while the BJP got 2 seats. The seats won by AITC were Chopra, Islampur, Goalpokhar, Chakulia, Karandighi, Hemtabad and Itahar, while the seats obtained by BJP included Kaliaganj and Raiganj.

Out of the total polled votes of 1,722,482, AITC secured a total of 918,653 (53%) votes while the BJP secured 643,709 (37%) of the votes. The INC having a vote share of 56,820 (3%) remained on third place, whereas the AIFB reached to the fourth position after securing 37,850 (2%) votes in the district.

UTTAR DINAJPUR District: First three candidates in each seat
Party with highest votes win that seat

Figure 33: Uttar Dinajpur District: Winners per constituency and top 3 candidates

4. CONCLUSIONS

The AITC won the election comprehensively, while the BJP consolidated its position as the main opposition party in West Bengal relegating the Left parties and Congress to an insignificant player in the politics of West Bengal. After the West Bengal 2021 election results, Mamata Banerjee emerged as one of the main challengers of BJP at the national arena of Indian politics. What lessons Bengal election offers to the country remains to be seen yet, but the state and central government’s handling of the second wave of Covid-19 crisis (in which many Indians lost lives) and associated social and economic crisis has kept the political battle open for the forthcoming Uttar Pradesh election in 2022 and the India’s general election in 2024. It has also infused fresh energy in opposition parties to challenge the election machinery and public image of Prime Minister Narendra Modi. With the global and national uncertainties looming large due to the Covid-19 crisis and a prediction of the third wave of the virus in the country, governments both at the state and the central level need to do much more than business as usual to win the trust of the people, if they want to acquire significant position in elections

Annex 1: Bankura District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Bankura	GEN	BJP	Niladri Sekhar Dana	1	95,466	1,468
Bankura	GEN	AITC	Sayantika Banerjee	2	93,998	80,234
Bankura	GEN	INC	Radharani Banerjee	3	13,764	9,257
Barjora	GEN	AITC	Alok Mukherjee	1	93,290	3,269
Barjora	GEN	BJP	Supriti Chatterjee	2	90,021	64,786
Barjora	GEN	CPM	Sujit Chakraborty	3	25,235	20,332
Bishnupur	GEN	BJP	Tanmay Ghosh (Bumba)	1	89,689	11,420
Bishnupur	GEN	AITC	Archita Bid	2	78,269	62,455
Bishnupur	GEN	INC	Debu Chatterjee	3	15,814	12,395
Chhatna	GEN	BJP	Satyanarayan Mukhopadhyay	1	90,233	7,164
Chhatna	GEN	AITC	Subasish Batabyal	2	83,069	73,369
Chhatna	GEN	RSP	Falguni Mukherjee	3	9,700	6,186
Indus	SC	BJP	Nirmal Kumar Dhara	1	104,936	7,220
Indus	SC	AITC	Runu Mete	2	97,716	85,097
Indus	SC	CPM	Nayan Kumar Shill (Bagdi)	3	12,619	9,437
Katulpur	SC	BJP	Harakali Protiher	1	106,022	11,785
Katulpur	SC	AITC	Sangeeta Malik	2	94,237	76,480
Katulpur	SC	INC	Akshay Santra	3	17,757	15,238
Onda	GEN	BJP	Amarnath Shakha	1	104,940	11,551
Onda	GEN	AITC	Arup Kumar Khan	2	93,389	77,776
Onda	GEN	AIFB	Tarapada Chakrabarti	3	15,613	10,734
Raipur	ST	AITC	Mrityunjoy Murmu	1	101,043	19,398
Raipur	ST	BJP	Sudhanshu Hansda	2	81,645	75,052
Raipur	ST	RSSCMJP	Milan Mandi	3	6,593	3,607
Ranibundh	ST	AITC	Jyotsna Mandi	1	90,928	3,939
Ranibundh	ST	BJP	Kshudiram Tudu	2	86,989	66,932
Ranibundh	ST	CPM	Deblina Hembram	3	20,057	15,250
Saltora	SC	BJP	Bauri Chandana	1	91,648	4,145
Saltora	SC	AITC	Sontosh Kumar Mondal	2	87,503	73,419
Saltora	SC	CPM	Nandadulal Bauri	3	14,084	10,530
Sonamukhi	SC	BJP	Dibakar Gharami	1	98,161	10,888
Sonamukhi	SC	AITC	Dr. Shyamal Santra	2	87,273	71,548
Sonamukhi	SC	CPM	Ajit Ray	3	15,725	12,953
Taldangra	GEN	AITC	Arup Chakraborty	1	92,026	12,377
Taldangra	GEN	BJP	Shyamal Kumar Sarkar (Benu)	2	79,649	56,460
Taldangra	GEN	CPM	Manoranjan Patra	3	23,189	19,671

Annex 2: Bardhaman District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Asansol Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Agnimitra Paul	1	87,881	4,487
Asansol Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Sayani Ghosh	2	83,394	67,422
Asansol Dakshin	GEN	CPM	Prasanta Ghosh	3	15,972	12,506
Asansol Uttar	GEN	AITC	Ghatak Moloy	1	100,931	21,110
Asansol Uttar	GEN	BJP	Krishnendu Mukherjee	2	79,821	75,350
Asansol Uttar	GEN	RSSCMJP	Mohammad Mustaqim	3	4,471	1,123
Ausgram	SC	AITC	Abhedananda Thander	1	100,392	11,815
Ausgram	SC	BJP	Kalita Maji	2	88,577	68,178
Ausgram	SC	CPM	Chanchal Kumar Majhi	3	20,399	16,360
Barbani	GEN	AITC	Bidhan Upadhyay	1	88,430	23,457
Barbani	GEN	BJP	Arijit Roy	2	64,973	56,011
Barbani	GEN	INC	Ranendra Nath Bagchi	3	8,962	5,923
Bardhaman Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Khokan Das	1	91,015	8,105
Bardhaman Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Sandip Nandi	2	82,910	59,564
Bardhaman Dakshin	GEN	CPM	Pritha Tah	3	23,346	19,639
Bardhaman Uttar	SC	AITC	Nisith Kumar Malik	1	111,211	17,268
Bardhaman Uttar	SC	BJP	Radha Kanta Roy	2	93,943	62,915
Bardhaman Uttar	SC	CPM	Chandi Choran Let	3	31,028	27,681
Bhatar	GEN	AITC	Adhikari Mangobinda	1	108,028	31,741
Bhatar	GEN	BJP	Mahendranath Kowar	2	76,287	56,680
Bhatar	GEN	CPM	Nazrul Haque	3	19,607	15,261
Durgapur Paschim	GEN	BJP	Lakshman Chandra Ghorui	1	91,186	14,664
Durgapur Paschim	GEN	AITC	Biswanath Parial	2	76,522	58,492
Durgapur Paschim	GEN	INC	Debesh Chakraborty	3	18,030	15,406
Durgapur Purba	GEN	AITC	Pradip Mazumdar	1	79,303	3,746
Durgapur Purba	GEN	BJP	Colonel Diptansu Chaudhury	2	75,557	46,494
Durgapur Purba	GEN	CPM	Abhas Ray Chaudhuri	3	29,063	26,435
Galsi	SC	AITC	Nepal Ghorui	1	109,504	19,262
Galsi	SC	BJP	Bikash Biswas	2	90,242	73,222
Galsi	SC	AIFB	Nandalal Pondit	3	17,020	13,502
Jamalpur	SC	AITC	Alok Kumar Majhi	1	96,999	17,971
Jamalpur	SC	BJP	Balaram Bapari	2	79,028	55,730
Jamalpur	SC	CPM	Samar Hazra	3	23,298	20,433
Jamuraia	GEN	AITC	Hareram Singh	1	71,002	8,051
Jamuraia	GEN	BJP	Tapas Kumar Roy	2	62,951	38,133
Jamuraia	GEN	CPM	Aishe Ghosh	3	24,818	22,409
Kalna	SC	AITC	Deboprasad Bag (Poltu)	1	96,073	7,478
Kalna	SC	BJP	Biswajit Kundu	2	88,595	69,590
Kalna	SC	CPM	Nirab Khan	3	19,005	16,498
Katwa	GEN	AITC	Rabindranath Chatterjee	1	107,894	9,155
Katwa	GEN	BJP	Shyama Majumdar	2	98,739	85,763

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Katwa	GEN	INC	Prabir Ganguli	3	12,976	11,196
Ketugram	GEN	AITC	Sekh Sahonawez	1	100,226	12,683
Ketugram	GEN	BJP	Anadi Ghosh (Mathura)	2	87,543	67,451
Ketugram	GEN	CPM	Mizanul Kabir (Dhiraj)	3	20,092	16,472
Khandaghosh	SC	AITC	Nabin Chandra Bag	1	104,264	20,886
Khandaghosh	SC	BJP	Bijan Mandal	2	83,378	60,455
Khandaghosh	SC	CPM	Asima Roy	3	22,923	19,458
Kulti	GEN	BJP	Ajay Kumar Poddar	1	81,112	679
Kulti	GEN	AITC	Ujjal Chatterjee	2	80,433	74,638
Kulti	GEN	INC	Chandi Das Chatterjee	3	5,795	2,242
Mangalkot	GEN	AITC	Apurba Chowdhury (Achal)	1	107,596	22,337
Mangalkot	GEN	BJP	Rana Protap Goswami	2	85,259	68,476
Mangalkot	GEN	CPM	Choudhury Sahajahan	3	16,783	12,957
Memari	GEN	AITC	Madhusudan Bhattacharya	1	104,851	23,078
Memari	GEN	BJP	Bhismadeb Bhattacharya	2	81,773	56,155
Memari	GEN	CPM	Sanat Banerjee	3	25,618	23,497
Monteswar	GEN	AITC	Chowdhury Siddiqullah	1	105,460	31,805
Monteswar	GEN	BJP	Saikat Panja	2	73,655	48,915
Monteswar	GEN	CPM	Anupam Ghosh	3	24,740	22,863
Pandabeswar	GEN	AITC	Narendranath Chakraborty	1	73,922	3,803
Pandabeswar	GEN	BJP	Kumar Jitendra Tewari	2	70,119	57,923
Pandabeswar	GEN	CPM	Subhas Bauri	3	12,196	9,461
Purbasthali Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Swapan Debnath	1	105,698	17,410
Purbasthali Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Rajib Kumar Bhowmick	2	88,288	73,227
Purbasthali Dakshin	GEN	INC	Abhijit Bhattacharyya	3	15,061	11,956
Purbasthali Uttar	GEN	AITC	Tapan Chatterjee	1	92,421	6,706
Purbasthali Uttar	GEN	BJP	Gobardhan Das	2	85,715	57,581
Purbasthali Uttar	GEN	CPM	Pradip Kumar Saha	3	28,134	26,227
Raina	SC	AITC	Shampa Dhara	1	108,752	18,205
Raina	SC	BJP	Manik Roy	2	90,547	65,215
Raina	SC	CPM	Basudeb Khan	3	25,332	23,461
Raniganj	GEN	AITC	Tapas Banerjee	1	78,164	3,556
Raniganj	GEN	BJP	Dr. Bijan Mukherjee	2	74,608	52,920
Raniganj	GEN	CPM	Hemant Kumar Prabhakar	3	21,688	19,682

Annex 3: Birbhum District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Bolpur	GEN	AITC	Sinha Chandranath	1	116,443	22,280
Bolpur	GEN	BJP	Anirban Ganguly	2	94,163	84,198
Bolpur	GEN	RSP	Tapan Hore	3	9,965	6,628
Dubrajpur	SC	BJP	Anup Kumar Saha	1	98,083	3,863
Dubrajpur	SC	AITC	Debabrata Saha	2	94,220	88,206
Dubrajpur	SC	AIFB	Bijoy Bagdi	3	6,014	2,857
Hansan	GEN	AITC	Dr. Asok Kumar Chattopadhyay	1	108,289	50,613
Hansan	GEN	BJP	Nikhil Banerjee	2	57,676	17,861
Hansan	GEN	INC	Miltan Rasid	3	39,815	37,395
Labhpur	GEN	AITC	Abhijit Sinha (Rana)	1	108,423	17,975
Labhpur	GEN	BJP	Biswajit Mondal	2	90,448	83,969
Labhpur	GEN	CPM	Syed Mahfuzul Karim	3	6,479	3,422
Mayureswar	GEN	AITC	Abhijit Roy	1	100,425	12,075
Mayureswar	GEN	BJP	Shyamapada Mondal	2	88,350	82,788
Mayureswar	GEN	RSSCMJP	Kashinath Pal	3	5,562	2,759
Murarai	GEN	AITC	Dr Mosarraf Hossain	1	146,496	98,246
Murarai	GEN	BJP	Debasish Roy	2	48,250	30,963
Murarai	GEN	INC	Asif Ekbal	3	17,287	15,430
Nalhati	GEN	AITC	Rajendra Prasad Singh (Raju Singh)	1	117,438	56,905
Nalhati	GEN	BJP	Tapas Kumar Yadav(Ananda Yadav)	2	60,533	39,205
Nalhati	GEN	AIFB	Dipak Chatterjee	3	21,328	19,428
Nanoor	SC	AITC	Bidhan Chandra Majhi	1	112,116	6,670
Nanoor	SC	BJP	Tarakeswar Saha	2	105,446	92,568
Nanoor	SC	CPM	Shyamali Pradhan	3	12,878	10,139
Rampurhat	GEN	AITC	Asish Banerjee	1	103,276	8,472
Rampurhat	GEN	BJP	Subhasis Choudhury (Khokan)	2	94,804	83,097
Rampurhat	GEN	CPM	Sanjib Barman (Gopi)	3	11,707	8,326
Sainthia	SC	AITC	Nilabati Saha	1	110,572	15,243
Sainthia	SC	BJP	Piya Saha	2	95,329	84,960
Sainthia	SC	CPM	Mausumi Konai	3	10,369	8,271
Suri	GEN	AITC	Bikash Roychoudhury	1	105,871	7,320
Suri	GEN	BJP	Chattopadhyay Jagannath	2	98,551	90,284
Suri	GEN	INC	Chanchal Chatterjee	3	8,267	6,183

Annex 4: Cooch Behar District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Cooch Behar Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Nikhil Ranjan Dey	1	91,560	4,931
Cooch Behar Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Avijit De Bhowmik	2	86,629	76,383
Cooch Behar Dakshin	GEN	AIFB	Akshay Thakur	3	10,246	8,761
Cooch Behar Uttar	SC	BJP	Sukumar Roy	1	120,483	14,615
Cooch Behar Uttar	SC	AITC	Binay Krishna Barman	2	105,868	94,393
Cooch Behar Uttar	SC	AIFB	Nagendra Nath Roy	3	11,475	9,905
Dinhata	GEN	BJP	Nisith Pramanik	1	116,035	57
Dinhata	GEN	AITC	Udayan Guha	2	115,978	109,909
Dinhata	GEN	AIFB	Abdur Rouf	3	6,069	4,532
Mathabhanga	SC	BJP	Sushil Barman	1	113,249	26,134
Mathabhanga	SC	AITC	Girindra Nath Barman	2	87,115	79,397
Mathabhanga	SC	CPM	Ashok Barman	3	7,718	6,275
Mekliganj	SC	AITC	Adhikary Paresh Chandra	1	99,338	14,685
Mekliganj	SC	BJP	Dadhiram Ray	2	84,653	77,800
Mekliganj	SC	AIFB	Gobinda Chandra Roy	3	6,853	4,406
Natabari	GEN	BJP	Mihir Goswami	1	111,743	23,440
Natabari	GEN	AITC	Rabindra Nath Ghosh	2	88,303	76,464
Natabari	GEN	CPM	Akik Hassan	3	11,839	10,498
Sitai	SC	AITC	Jagadish Chandra Barma Basunia	1	117,908	10,112
Sitai	SC	BJP	Dipak Kumar Roy	2	107,796	103,832
Sitai	SC	INC	Keshab Chandra Ray	3	3,964	1,573
Sitalkuchi	SC	BJP	Baren Chandra Barman	1	124,955	17,815
Sitalkuchi	SC	AITC	Partha Pratim Ray	2	107,140	100,420
Sitalkuchi	SC	CPM	Sudhangshu Pramanik	3	6,720	3,977
Tufanganj	GEN	BJP	Malati Rava Roy	1	114,503	31,198
Tufanganj	GEN	AITC	Pranab Kumar Dey	2	83,305	77,332
Tufanganj	GEN	INC	Rabin Roy	3	5,973	3,904

Annex 5: Dakshin Dinajpur District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Balurghat	GEN	BJP	Ashok Kumar Lahiri	1	72,129	13,436
Balurghat	GEN	AITC	Sekhar Dasgupta	2	58,693	42,540
Balurghat	GEN	RSP	Sucheta Biswas	3	16,153	14,323
Gangarampur	SC	BJP	Satyendra Nath Ray	1	88,724	4,592
Gangarampur	SC	AITC	Goutam Das	2	84,132	71,859
Gangarampur	SC	CPM	Nanda Lal Hazra	3	12,273	11,104
Harirampur	GEN	AITC	Biplab Mitra	1	96,131	22,672
Harirampur	GEN	BJP	Nilanjan Roy	2	73,459	61,015
Harirampur	GEN	CPM	Rafikul Islam	3	12,444	10,613
Kumarganj	GEN	AITC	Toraf Hossain Mandal	1	89,763	29,367
Kumarganj	GEN	BJP	Manas Sarkar	2	60,396	42,918
Kumarganj	GEN	INC	Chaudhuri Nargis Banu	3	17,478	16,263
Kushmandi	SC	AITC	Rekha Roy	1	89,968	12,584
Kushmandi	SC	BJP	Ranjit Kumar Roy	2	77,384	64,813
Kushmandi	SC	RSP	Narmada Chandra Roy	3	12,571	10,973
Tapan	ST	BJP	Budhrai Tudu	1	84,381	1,650
Tapan	ST	AITC	Kalpana Kisku	2	82,731	70,643
Tapan	ST	RSP	Raghu Urow	3	12,088	9,942

Annex 6: Darjeeling District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Darjeeling	GEN	BJP	Neeraj Tamang Zimba	1	68,907	21,276
Darjeeling	GEN	IND	Keshav Raj Sharma	2	47,631	9,391
Darjeeling	GEN	IND	Pemba Tshering	3	38,240	35,385
Kalimpong	GEN	IND	Ruden Sada Lepcha	1	58,206	3,870
Kalimpong	GEN	BJP	Suva Pradhan	2	54,336	22,480
Kalimpong	GEN	IND	Dr. R.b. Bhujel	3	31,856	29,696
Kurseong	GEN	BJP	Bishnu Prasad Sharma (Alias B.p. Bajgain)	1	73,475	15,515
Kurseong	GEN	IND	Tshering Lama	2	57,960	24,866
Kurseong	GEN	IND	Narbu Lama	3	33,094	30,549
Matigara-Naxalbari	SC	BJP	Anandamay Barman	1	139,785	70,848
Matigara-Naxalbari	SC	AITC	Rajen Sundas	2	68,937	45,877
Matigara-Naxalbari	SC	INC	Sankar Malakar	3	23,060	19,148
Phansidewa	ST	BJP	Durga Murmu	1	105,651	27,711
Phansidewa	ST	AITC	Chhotan Kisku	2	77,940	65,125
Phansidewa	ST	INC	Sunil Chandra Tirkey	3	12,815	10,028
Siliguri	GEN	BJP	Sankar Ghosh	1	89,370	35,586
Siliguri	GEN	AITC	Dr. Omprakash Mishra	2	53,784	24,949
Siliguri	GEN	CPM	Asok Bhattacharya	3	28,835	26,761

Annex 7: Hooghly District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Arambag	SC	BJP	Madhusudan Bag	1	103,108	7,172
Arambag	SC	AITC	Sujata Mondal	2	95,936	80,971
Arambag	SC	CPM	Sakti Mohon Malik	3	14,965	11,794
Balagarh	SC	AITC	Manoranjan Bapari	1	100,364	5,784
Balagarh	SC	BJP	Subhas Chandra Haldar	2	94,580	74,814
Balagarh	SC	CPM	Mahamaya Mondal	3	19,766	16,661
Champdani	GEN	AITC	Arindam Guin (Bubai)	1	100,972	30,078
Champdani	GEN	BJP	Dilip Singh	2	70,894	47,622
Champdani	GEN	INC	Abdul Mannan	3	23,272	19,925
Chandannagore	GEN	AITC	Indranil Sen	1	86,778	31,029
Chandannagore	GEN	BJP	Deepanjan Kumar Guha	2	55,749	22,047
Chandannagore	GEN	CPM	Gautam Sarkar	3	33,702	30,679
Chanditala	GEN	AITC	Swati Khandoker	1	103,118	41,347
Chanditala	GEN	BJP	Debashish Dasgupta(Yash D Gupta)	2	61,771	24,610
Chanditala	GEN	CPM	Md. Salim	3	37,161	35,005
Chunchura	GEN	AITC	Asit Mazumder (Tapan)	1	117,104	18,417
Chunchura	GEN	BJP	Locket Chatterjee	2	98,687	69,910
Chunchura	GEN	AIFB	Pranab Kumar Ghosh	3	28,777	24,439
Dhanekhali	SC	AITC	Asima Patra	1	124,776	30,159
Dhanekhali	SC	BJP	Tusar Kumar Majumdar	2	94,617	85,584
Dhanekhali	SC	INC	Anirban Saha	3	9,033	5,803
Goghat	SC	BJP	Biswanath Karak	1	102,227	4,147
Goghat	SC	AITC	Manas Majumdar	2	98,080	83,702
Goghat	SC	AIFB	Shiba Prasad Malick	3	14,378	11,896
Haripal	GEN	AITC	Dr. Karabi Manna	1	110,215	23,072
Haripal	GEN	BJP	Samiran Mitra	2	87,143	71,348
Haripal	GEN	RSSCMJ P	Simal Saren	3	15,795	12,428
Jangipara	GEN	AITC	Snehasis Chakraborty	1	101,885	17,926
Jangipara	GEN	BJP	Debjit Sarkar	2	83,959	66,203
Jangipara	GEN	RSSCMJ P	Sk. Mainuddin	3	17,756	14,716
Khanakul	GEN	BJP	Susanta Ghosh	1	107,403	12,884
Khanakul	GEN	AITC	Munsi Nazbul Karim	2	94,519	85,787
Khanakul	GEN	RSSCMJ P	Faisal Khan	3	8,732	5,454
Pandua	GEN	AITC	Dr. Ratna De Nag	1	102,874	31,858
Pandua	GEN	BJP	Partha Sharma	2	71,016	29,542
Pandua	GEN	CPM	Amjad Hossain Sk.	3	41,474	39,310
Pursurah	GEN	BJP	Biman Ghosh	1	119,334	28,178
Pursurah	GEN	AITC	Dilip Yadav	2	91,156	83,328
Pursurah	GEN	INC	Monika Malik Ghosh	3	7,828	5,040
Saptagram	GEN	AITC	Tapan Dasgupta	1	93,328	9,772
Saptagram	GEN	BJP	Debabrata Biswas	2	83,556	75,224
Saptagram	GEN	INC	Pabitra Deb	3	8,332	5,295

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Singur	GEN	AITC	Becharam Manna	1	101,077	25,923
Singur	GEN	BJP	Rabindranath Bhattacharya	2	75,154	45,138
Singur	GEN	CPM	Srijan Bhattacharyya	3	30,016	27,671
Sreerampur	GEN	AITC	Dr. Sudipto Roy	1	93,021	23,433
Sreerampur	GEN	BJP	Kabir Shankar Bose	2	69,588	50,187
Sreerampur	GEN	INC	Alok Ranjan Banerjee	3	19,401	17,001
Tarakeswar	GEN	AITC	Ramendu Sinharay	1	96,698	7,484
Tarakeswar	GEN	BJP	Dr. Swapan Dasgupta	2	89,214	74,619
Tarakeswar	GEN	CPM	Surajit Ghosh	3	14,595	11,843
Uttarpara	GEN	AITC	Kanchan Mullick	1	93,878	35,989
Uttarpara	GEN	BJP	Prabir Kumar Ghosal	2	57,889	15,171
Uttarpara	GEN	CPM	Rajat Banerjee (Bappa)	3	42,718	39,365

Annex 8: Howrah District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Amta	GEN	AITC	Sukanta Kumar Paul	1	102,445	26,205
Amta	GEN	BJP	Debtanu Bhattacharya	2	76,240	51,131
Amta	GEN	INC	Asit Mitra	3	25,109	23,807
Bagnan	GEN	AITC	Arunava Sen (Raja)	1	106,042	30,120
Bagnan	GEN	BJP	Anupam Mallik	2	75,922	61,367
Bagnan	GEN	CPM	Sk Bosir Ahmed	3	14,555	13,007
Bally	GEN	AITC	Rana Chatterjee	1	53,347	6,237
Bally	GEN	BJP	Baishali Dalmiya	2	47,110	25,070
Bally	GEN	CPM	Dipsita Dhar	3	22,040	20,835
Domjur	GEN	AITC	Kalyan Ghosh	1	130,499	42,620
Domjur	GEN	BJP	Rajib Banerjee S/O- Late Dhananjoy Banerjee	2	87,879	65,111
Domjur	GEN	CPM	Uttam Bera	3	22,768	19,913
Howrah Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Nandita Chowdhury	1	116,839	50,569
Howrah Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Rantidev Sengupta	2	66,270	38,983
Howrah Dakshin	GEN	CPM	Sumitro Adhikary	3	27,287	24,339
Howrah Madhya	GEN	AITC	Arup Roy, S/O Late Prabhat Roy	1	111,554	46,547
Howrah Madhya	GEN	BJP	Sanjay Singh	2	65,007	52,065
Howrah Madhya	GEN	INC	Palash Bhandari	3	12,942	10,207
Howrah Uttar	GEN	AITC	Gautam Chowdhuri	1	71,575	5,522
Howrah Uttar	GEN	BJP	Umesh Rai	2	66,053	57,920
Howrah Uttar	GEN	CPM	Pawan Kumar Singh	3	8,133	6,463
Jagatballavpur	GEN	AITC	Sitanath Ghosh	1	116,562	29,196
Jagatballavpur	GEN	BJP	Anupam Ghosh	2	87,366	62,004
Jagatballavpur	GEN	RSSC MJP	Sk Sabbir Ahmed	3	25,362	22,593
Panchla	GEN	AITC	Gulsan Mullick	1	104,572	32,751
Panchla	GEN	BJP	Mohit Lal Ghanti	2	71,821	36,245
Panchla	GEN	RSSC MJP	Abdul Jalil Sk	3	35,576	33,165
Sankrail	SC	AITC	Priya Paul	1	111,888	40,427
Sankrail	SC	BJP	Probhakar Pandit	2	71,461	37,317

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Sankrail	SC	CPM	Samir Malick	3	34,144	32,294
Shibpur	GEN	AITC	Manoj Tiwary	1	92,372	32,603
Shibpur	GEN	BJP	Rathin Chakrabarty	2	59,769	34,799
Shibpur	GEN	AIFB	Jagannath Bhattacharyya	3	24,970	23,058
Shyampur	GEN	AITC	Kalipada Mandal	1	114,804	31,511
Shyampur	GEN	BJP	Tnusree Chakraborty	2	83,293	62,885
Shyampur	GEN	INC	Amitabha Chakraborti	3	20,408	19,266
Udaynarayanpur	GEN	AITC	Samir Kumar Panja	1	101,510	13,998
Udaynarayanpur	GEN	BJP	Sumit Ranjan Karar	2	87,512	82,334
Udaynarayanpur	GEN	INC	Aloke Koley	3	5,178	3,460
Uluberia Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Pulak Roy	1	101,880	28,438
Uluberia Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Papia Dey (Adhikary)	2	73,442	52,332
Uluberia Dakshin	GEN	AIFB	Sk Kutub Uddin Ahmed	3	21,110	19,636
Uluberia Purba	GEN	AITC	Bidesh Ranjan Bose	1	86,526	17,126
Uluberia Purba	GEN	BJP	Pratyush Mandal	2	69,400	38,942
Uluberia Purba	GEN	RSSC MJP	Abbas Uddin Khan	3	30,458	28,347
Uluberia Uttar	SC	AITC	Dr. Nirmal Maji	1	91,501	21,003
Uluberia Uttar	SC	BJP	Chiran Bera	2	70,498	51,206
Uluberia Uttar	SC	CPM	Ashok Dalui	3	19,292	18,044

Annex 9: Jalpaiguri District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Alipurduars	GEN	BJP	Suman Kanjilal	1	107,333	16,007
Alipurduars	GEN	AITC	Sourav Chakraborty (Ghutis)	2	91,326	75,675
Alipurduars	GEN	INC	Deba Prasad Roy	3	15,651	13,300
Dabgram-Phulbari	GEN	BJP	Sikha Chatterjee	1	129,088	27,593
Dabgram-Phulbari	GEN	AITC	Goutam Deb	2	101,495	83,497
Dabgram-Phulbari	GEN	CPM	Dilip Singh	3	17,998	14,619
Dhupguri	SC	BJP	Bishnu Pada Ray	1	104,688	4,355
Dhupguri	SC	AITC	Mitali Roy	2	100,333	87,226
Dhupguri	SC	CPM	Pradip Kumar Roy	3	13,107	10,929
Falakata	SC	BJP	Dipak Barman	1	102,993	3,990
Falakata	SC	AITC	Subhash Chandra Roy	2	99,003	88,231
Falakata	SC	CPM	Kshitish Chandra Ray	3	10,772	8,802
Jalpaiguri	SC	AITC	Dr. Pradip Kumar Barma	1	95,668	941
Jalpaiguri	SC	BJP	Soujit Singha (Piku)	2	94,727	70,499
Jalpaiguri	SC	INC	Sukhbilas Barma	3	24,228	20,847
Kalchini	ST	BJP	Bishal Lama	1	103,104	28,576
Kalchini	ST	AITC	Passang Lama	2	74,528	69,046
Kalchini	ST	INC	Avijit Narjinary	3	5,482	3,057
Kumargram	ST	BJP	Manoj Kumar Oraon	1	111,974	11,001
Kumargram	ST	AITC	Leos Kujur (Urao)	2	100,973	89,720
Kumargram	ST	RSP	Kishor Minj	3	11,253	8,535
Madarihat	ST	BJP	Manoj Tigga	1	90,718	29,685
Madarihat	ST	AITC	Rajesh Lakra	2	61,033	53,961

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Madarihat	ST	RSP	Subhash Lohar	3	7,072	4,450
Mal	ST	AITC	Bulu Chik Baraik	1	99,086	5,465
Mal	ST	BJP	Mahesh Bagey	2	93,621	82,692
Mal	ST	CPM	Manu Oraon	3	10,929	6,230
Maynaguri	SC	BJP	Kaushik Roy	1	115,306	11,911
Maynaguri	SC	AITC	Manoj Roy	2	103,395	97,635
Maynaguri	SC	RSP	Naresh Chandra Roy	3	5,760	2,665
Nagrakata	ST	BJP	Puna Bhengra	1	83,707	19,038
Nagrakata	ST	AITC	Joseph Munda	2	64,669	53,068
Nagrakata	ST	INC	Sukbir Subba	3	11,601	6,675
Rajganj	SC	AITC	Khageswar Roy	1	104,641	15,773
Rajganj	SC	BJP	Supen Roy	2	88,868	76,760
Rajganj	SC	CPM	Ratan Kumar Roy	3	12,108	8,933

Annex 10: Kolkata Corporation District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Ballygunge	GEN	AITC	Subrata Mukherjee	1	106,585	75,359
Ballygunge	GEN	BJP	Lokenath Chatterjee	2	31,226	22,752
Ballygunge	GEN	CPM	Dr. Fuad Halim	3	8,474	7,157
Belehata	GEN	AITC	Paresh Paul	1	103,182	67,140
Belehata	GEN	BJP	Kashinath Biswas	2	36,042	21,997
Belehata	GEN	CPM	Rajib Biswas	3	14,045	12,481
Bhabanipur	GEN	AITC	Sobhandeb Chattopadhyay	1	73,505	28,719
Bhabanipur	GEN	BJP	Rudranil Ghosh	2	44,786	39,575
Bhabanipur	GEN	INC	Md. Shadab Khan	3	5,211	3,641
Chowrangee	GEN	AITC	Bandyopadhyay Nayna	1	70,101	45,344
Chowrangee	GEN	BJP	Devdutta Maji	2	24,757	10,491
Chowrangee	GEN	INC	Santosh Kumar Pathak	3	14,266	13,054
Entally	GEN	AITC	Swarna Kamal Saha	1	101,709	58,257
Entally	GEN	BJP	Priyanka Tibrewal	2	43,452	39,098
Entally	GEN	RSSCMJP	Md. Iqbal Alam	3	4,354	2,420
Jorasanko	GEN	AITC	Vivek Gupta	1	52,123	12,743
Jorasanko	GEN	BJP	Meena Devi Purohit	2	39,380	34,611
Jorasanko	GEN	INC	Ajmal Khan	3	4,769	3,741
Kashipur-Belgachia	GEN	AITC	Atin Ghosh	1	27,482	12,786
Kashipur-Belgachia	GEN	BJP	Sibaji Sinha Roy	2	14,696	8,495
Kashipur-Belgachia	GEN	CPM	Pratip Dasgupta	3	6,201	5,649
Kolkata Port	GEN	AITC	Firhad Hakim	1	105,543	68,554
Kolkata Port	GEN	BJP	Awadh Kishore Gupta	2	36,989	31,399
Kolkata Port	GEN	INC	Md Mukhtar	3	5,590	4,230
Maniktala	GEN	AITC	Sadhan Pande	1	25,589	8,490
Maniktala	GEN	BJP	Kalyan Chaubey	2	17,099	12,677
Maniktala	GEN	CPM	Rupa Bagchi	3	4,422	3,874
Rashbehari	GEN	AITC	Debasish Kumar	1	65,704	21,414
Rashbehari	GEN	BJP	Lt. Gen. (Dr.) Subrata Saha	2	44,290	33,976

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Rashbehari	GEN	INC	Ashutosh Chatterjee	3	10,314	8,652
Shyampukur	GEN	AITC	Dr. Shashi Panja	1	55,785	22,520
Shyampukur	GEN	BJP	Sandipan Biswas	2	33,265	22,437
Shyampukur	GEN	AIFB	Jiban Prakash Saha	3	10,828	9,765

Annex 11: Maldah District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Baishnab Nagar	GEN	AITC	Chandana Sarkar	1	83,061	2,471
Baishnab Nagar	GEN	BJP	Swadhin Kumar Sarkar	2	80,590	43,147
Baishnab Nagar	GEN	INC	Azizul Hoque	3	37,443	35,161
Chanchal	GEN	AITC	Nihar Ranjan Ghosh	1	115,966	67,338
Chanchal	GEN	BJP	Dipankar Ram (Bankat)	2	48,628	17,282
Chanchal	GEN	INC	Asif Mehbub	3	31,346	30,132
Englishbazar	GEN	BJP	Sreerupa Mitra Chaudhury(Nirbhoy Didi)	1	107,755	20,099
Englishbazar	GEN	AITC	Krishnendu Narayan Choudhury	2	87,656	76,703
Englishbazar	GEN	CPM	Koushik Misra(Saheb)	3	10,953	7,757
Gazole	SC	BJP	Chinmoy Deb Barman	1	100,655	1,798
Gazole	SC	AITC	Basanti Barman	2	98,857	84,907
Gazole	SC	CPM	Arun Kumar Biswas	3	13,950	12,007
Habibpur	ST	BJP	Joyel Murmu	1	94,075	19,517
Habibpur	ST	AITC	Prodip Baskey	2	74,558	60,753
Habibpur	ST	CPM	Thakur Tudu	3	13,805	7,909
Harischandrapur	GEN	AITC	Tajmul Hossain	1	122,527	77,473
Harischandrapur	GEN	BJP	Md. Matibur Rahaman	2	45,054	15,658
Harischandrapur	GEN	INC	Alam Mostaque	3	29,396	27,923
Malatipur	GEN	AITC	Abdur Rahim Boxi	1	126,157	91,949
Malatipur	GEN	BJP	Mousumi Das	2	34,208	14,381
Malatipur	GEN	INC	Alberuni Zulkarnain	3	19,827	17,793
Maldaha	SC	BJP	Gopal Chandra Saha	1	93,398	15,456
Maldaha	SC	AITC	Ujjwal Kumar Chowdhury	2	77,942	51,379
Maldaha	SC	INC	Bhupendra Nath Halder (Arjun)	3	26,563	23,745
Manickchak	GEN	AITC	Sabitri Mitra	1	110,234	33,878
Manickchak	GEN	BJP	Gour Chandra Mandal	2	76,356	64,801
Manickchak	GEN	INC	Alam Mottakin	3	11,555	8,812
Mothabari	GEN	AITC	Yeasmin Sabina	1	97,397	56,573
Mothabari	GEN	BJP	Shyamchand Ghosh	2	40,824	23,921
Mothabari	GEN	INC	Dulal Sk	3	16,903	13,318
Ratua	GEN	AITC	Samar Mukherjee	1	130,674	75,650
Ratua	GEN	BJP	Abishek Singhanian	2	55,024	38,851
Ratua	GEN	INC	Khatun Najema	3	16,173	7,545
Sujapur	GEN	AITC	Md Abdul Ghani	1	152,445	130,163
Sujapur	GEN	INC	Isha Khan Choudhury	2	22,282	7,493
Sujapur	GEN	BJP	Sk Ziauddin	3	14,789	3,616

Annex 12: Murshidabad District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Baharampur	GEN	BJP	Subrata Maitra (Kanchan)	1	89,340	26,852
Baharampur	GEN	AITC	Naru Gopal Mukherjee	2	62,488	22,321
Baharampur	GEN	INC	Manoj Chakraborty	3	40,167	37,642
Beldanga	GEN	AITC	Hasanuzzaman Sk	1	112,862	53,832
Beldanga	GEN	BJP	Sumit Ghosh	2	59,030	32,081
Beldanga	GEN	INC	Safiujjaman Seikh	3	26,949	24,981
Bhagabangola	GEN	AITC	Idris Ali	1	153,795	106,008
Bhagabangola	GEN	CPM	Md. Kamal Hossain	2	47,787	31,080
Bhagabangola	GEN	BJP	Mehebus Alam	3	16,707	13,311
Bharatpur	GEN	AITC	Humayun Kabir	1	96,226	43,083
Bharatpur	GEN	BJP	Iman Kalyan Mukherjee	2	53,143	23,027
Bharatpur	GEN	INC	Kamalesh Chatterjee (Gopal)	3	30,116	27,535
Burwan	SC	AITC	Jiban Krishna Saha	1	81,890	2,749
Burwan	SC	BJP	Amiya Kumar Das	2	79,141	66,881
Burwan	SC	INC	Shiladitya Haldar	3	12,260	10,252
Domkal	GEN	AITC	Jafikul Islam	1	127,671	47,229
Domkal	GEN	CPM	Md. Mostafijur Rahaman (Rana)	2	80,442	68,094
Domkal	GEN	BJP	Biyamma Mondal (Rubia)	3	12,348	9,929
Farakka	GEN	AITC	Manirul Islam	1	102,319	59,945
Farakka	GEN	BJP	Ghosh Hemanta	2	42,374	6,169
Farakka	GEN	INC	Mainul Haque	3	36,205	34,558
Hariharpara	GEN	AITC	Niamot Sheikh	1	102,660	14,066
Hariharpara	GEN	INC	Mir Alamgir (Palash)	2	88,594	70,216
Hariharpara	GEN	BJP	Tanmoy Biswas	3	18,378	16,653
Jalangi	GEN	AITC	Abdur Razzak	1	123,840	79,276
Jalangi	GEN	CPM	Saiful Islam Molla	2	44,564	791
Jalangi	GEN	BJP	Chandan Mandal	3	43,773	39,584
Kandi	GEN	AITC	Apurba Sarkar (David)	1	95,399	38,080
Kandi	GEN	BJP	Goutam Roy	2	57,319	29,764
Kandi	GEN	INC	Shafiul Alam Khan (Bonu)	3	27,555	24,424
Khargram	SC	AITC	Ashis Marjit	1	93,255	32,573
Khargram	SC	BJP	Aditya Moulik	2	60,682	33,259
Khargram	SC	INC	Bipad Taran Bagdi	3	27,423	25,738
Lalgola	GEN	AITC	Ali Mohammad	1	107,860	60,707
Lalgola	GEN	INC	Abu Hena	2	47,153	17,689
Lalgola	GEN	BJP	Kalpana Ghosh	3	29,464	27,773
Murshidabad	GEN	BJP	Gouri Sankar Ghosh	1	95,967	2,491
Murshidabad	GEN	AITC	Shaoni Singha Roy	2	93,476	64,641
Murshidabad	GEN	INC	Neajuddin Sk	3	28,835	25,931
Nabagram	SC	AITC	Kanai Chandra Mondal	1	100,455	35,533
Nabagram	SC	BJP	Mohan Halder	2	64,922	25,793
Nabagram	SC	CPM	Kripalini Ghosh	3	39,129	36,500
Naoda	GEN	AITC	Sahina Momtaz Khan	1	117,684	74,153
Naoda	GEN	BJP	Anupam Mandal	2	43,531	11,943
Naoda	GEN	INC	Mosaraf Hossain Mondal (Madhu)	3	31,588	27,195
Raghunathganj	GEN	AITC	Akhruzzaman	1	126,834	98,313

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Raghunathganj	GEN	BJP	Golam Modaswer	2	28,521	12,277
Raghunathganj	GEN	IND	Nasir Saikh	3	16,244	3,445
Raninagar	GEN	AITC	Abdul Soumik Hossain	1	134,957	79,702
Raninagar	GEN	INC	Firoza Begam	2	55,255	34,117
Raninagar	GEN	BJP	Mst Masuara Khatun	3	21,138	18,364
Rejinagar	GEN	AITC	Rabiul Alam Chowdhury	1	118,494	68,268
Rejinagar	GEN	BJP	Arabinda Biswas	2	50,226	12,944
Rejinagar	GEN	INC	Kafiruddin Sk	3	37,282	35,722
Sagardighi	GEN	AITC	Subrata Saha	1	95,189	50,206
Sagardighi	GEN	BJP	Khatun Mafuja	2	44,983	8,639
Sagardighi	GEN	INC	Sk M Hasanuzzaman (Bappa)	3	36,344	32,894
Suti	GEN	AITC	Emani Biswas	1	127,351	70,701
Suti	GEN	BJP	Koushik Das	2	56,650	37,890
Suti	GEN	INC	Humayun Reza	3	18,760	10,754

Annex 13: Nadia District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Chakdaha	GEN	BJP	Bankim Chandra Ghosh	1	99,368	11,680
Chakdaha	GEN	AITC	Subhankar Singha (Jishu)	2	87,688	69,876
Chakdaha	GEN	CPM	Narayan Das Gupta	3	17,812	16,129
Chapra	GEN	AITC	Rukbanur Rahman	1	73,866	12,118
Chapra	GEN	IND	Jeber Sekh	2	61,748	3,580
Chapra	GEN	BJP	Kalyan Kumar Nandi	3	58,168	46,446
Haringhata	SC	BJP	Asim Kumar Sarkar	1	97,666	15,200
Haringhata	SC	AITC	Nilima Nag (Mallick)	2	82,466	57,666
Haringhata	SC	CPM	Alakesh Das	3	24,800	23,373
Kaliganj	GEN	AITC	Nasiruddin Ahamed (Lal)	1	111,696	46,987
Kaliganj	GEN	BJP	Abhijit Ghosh	2	64,709	39,633
Kaliganj	GEN	INC	Abul Kashem	3	25,076	23,025
Kalyani	SC	BJP	Ambika Roy	1	97,026	2,206
Kalyani	SC	AITC	Aniruddha Biswas	2	94,820	72,655
Kalyani	SC	CPM	Sabuj Das	3	22,165	19,588
Karimpur	GEN	AITC	Bimalendu Sinha Roy	1	110,911	23,575
Karimpur	GEN	BJP	Samarendranath Ghosh	2	87,336	70,151
Karimpur	GEN	CPM	Prabhas Majumdar	3	17,185	15,716
Krishnaganj	SC	BJP	Ashis Kumar Biswas	1	117,668	21,277
Krishnaganj	SC	AITC	Dr. Tapas Mandal	2	96,391	85,478
Krishnaganj	SC	CPM	Jhunu Baidya	3	10,913	8,814
Krishnanagar Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Ujjal Biswas	1	91,738	9,305
Krishnanagar Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Mahadev Sarkar	2	82,433	66,827
Krishnanagar Dakshin	GEN	CPM	Biswas Sumit	3	15,606	13,441
Krishnanagar Uttar	GEN	BJP	Mukul Roy	1	109,357	35,089
Krishnanagar Uttar	GEN	AITC	Koushani Mukherjee	2	74,268	62,861
Krishnanagar Uttar	GEN	INC	Silvi Saha	3	11,407	9,556
Nabadwip	GEN	AITC	Pundarikakshya Saha	1	102,170	18,571
Nabadwip	GEN	BJP	Sidhartha Shankar Naskar	2	83,599	65,059
Nabadwip	GEN	CPM	Swarnendu Sinha	3	18,540	16,196

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Nakashipara	GEN	AITC	Kallol Khan	1	104,812	21,271
Nakashipara	GEN	BJP	Santanu Dey	2	83,541	72,264
Nakashipara	GEN	IND	Tanmay Ganguli	3	11,277	5,912
Palashipara	GEN	AITC	Dr. Manik Bhattacharya	1	110,274	51,336
Palashipara	GEN	BJP	Bibhash Chandra Mandal	2	58,938	32,710
Palashipara	GEN	CPM	S.m. Sadi	3	26,228	24,532
Ranaghat Dakshin	SC	BJP	Mukut Mani Adhikari	1	119,260	16,515
Ranaghat Dakshin	SC	AITC	Barnali Dey Roy	2	102,745	87,621
Ranaghat Dakshin	SC	CPM	Rama Biswas	3	15,124	13,458
Ranaghat Uttar Paschim	GEN	BJP	Parthasarathi Chatterjee	1	113,637	23,128
Ranaghat Uttar Paschim	GEN	AITC	Sankar Singha	2	90,509	80,164
Ranaghat Uttar Paschim	GEN	INC	Bijayendu Biswas (Habu)	3	10,345	8,087
Ranaghat Uttar Purba	SC	BJP	Ashim Biswas	1	116,786	31,782
Ranaghat Uttar Purba	SC	AITC	Samir Kumar Poddar	2	85,004	79,800
Ranaghat Uttar Purba	SC	RSSCMJP	Dinesh Chandra Biswas	3	5,204	2,845
Santipur	GEN	BJP	Jagannath Sarkar	1	109,722	15,878
Santipur	GEN	AITC	Ajoy Dey	2	93,844	83,996
Santipur	GEN	INC	Ritzu Ghosal	3	9,848	7,463
Tehatta	GEN	AITC	Tapas Kumar Saha	1	97,848	6,915
Tehatta	GEN	BJP	Ashutosh Paul	2	90,933	67,694
Tehatta	GEN	CPM	Subodh Chandra Biswas	3	23,239	21,363

Annex 14: North 24 Parganas District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Amdanga	GEN	AITC	Rafiqur Rahaman	1	88,935	25,480
Amdanga	GEN	BJP	Joydev Manna	2	63,455	12,550
Amdanga	GEN	RSSCMJP	Jamal Uddin	3	50,905	48,581
Ashoknagar	GEN	AITC	Narayan Goswami	1	93,587	23,532
Ashoknagar	GEN	BJP	Tanuja Chakraborty	2	70,055	24,260
Ashoknagar	GEN	RSSCMJP	Tapas Banerjee	3	45,795	44,184
Baduria	GEN	AITC	Abdur Rahim Quazi	1	109,701	56,444
Baduria	GEN	BJP	Sukalyan Baidya	2	53,257	8,026
Baduria	GEN	INC	Abdus Sattar	3	45,231	43,278
Bagdah	SC	BJP	Biswajit Das	1	108,111	9,792
Bagdah	SC	AITC	Paritosh Kumar Saha	2	98,319	90,069
Bagdah	SC	INC	Kirttaniya Prabir (Bapi)	3	8,250	6,010
Baranagar	GEN	AITC	Tapas Roy	1	85,615	35,147
Baranagar	GEN	BJP	Parno Mittra	2	50,468	30,333
Baranagar	GEN	INC	Amal Kumar Mukhopadhyay	3	20,135	17,757
Barasat	GEN	AITC	Chiranjeet Chakrabarti	1	104,431	23,783
Barasat	GEN	BJP	Sankar Chatterjee	2	80,648	46,477
Barasat	GEN	AIFB	Sanjib Chattopadhyay	3	34,171	31,483
Barrackpur	GEN	AITC	Raju Chakraborty (Raj)	1	68,887	9,222
Barrackpur	GEN	BJP	Chandramani Shukla	2	59,665	43,520
Barrackpur	GEN	CPM	Debasish Bhowmick	3	16,145	14,215

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Basirhat Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Dr. Saptarshi Banerjee	1	115,873	24,468
Basirhat Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Tarak Nath Ghosh	2	91,405	68,316
Basirhat Dakshin	GEN	INC	Amit Majumdar	3	23,089	21,400
Basirhat Uttar	GEN	AITC	Rafikul Islam Mondal	1	137,216	89,351
Basirhat Uttar	GEN	RSSCMJP	Md Baijid Amin	2	47,865	360
Basirhat Uttar	GEN	BJP	Narayan Chandra Mondal	3	47,505	45,491
Bhatpara	GEN	BJP	Pawan Kumar Singh	1	57,244	13,687
Bhatpara	GEN	AITC	Jitendra Shaw (Jitu)	2	43,557	41,388
Bhatpara	GEN	INC	Dharmendra Shaw	3	2,169	1,009
Bidhannagar	GEN	AITC	Sujit Bose	1	75,912	7,997
Bidhannagar	GEN	BJP	Sabya Sachi Dutta	2	67,915	55,094
Bidhannagar	GEN	INC	Abhisek Banerjee	3	12,821	10,608
Bijpur	GEN	AITC	Subodh Adhikary	1	66,625	13,347
Bijpur	GEN	BJP	Subhranshu Roy	2	53,278	38,788
Bijpur	GEN	CPM	Sukanta Rakshit (Babin)	3	14,490	12,948
Bongaon Dakshin	SC	BJP	Swapan Majumder	1	97,828	2,004
Bongaon Dakshin	SC	AITC	Alo Rani Sarkar	2	95,824	85,755
Bongaon Dakshin	SC	CPM	Tapas Kumar Biswas	3	10,069	8,527
Bongaon Uttar	SC	BJP	Ashok Kirtania	1	97,761	10,488
Bongaon Uttar	SC	AITC	Shyamal Roy	2	87,273	73,222
Bongaon Uttar	SC	CPM	Pijush Kanti Saha	3	14,051	12,218
Deganga	GEN	AITC	Rahima Mondal	1	100,105	32,537
Deganga	GEN	RSSCMJP	Karim Ali	2	67,568	29,122
Deganga	GEN	BJP	Dipika Chattarjee	3	38,446	35,504
Dum Dum	GEN	AITC	Brtya Basu	1	87,999	26,731
Dum Dum	GEN	BJP	Bimalshankar Nanda	2	61,268	30,615
Dum Dum	GEN	CPM	Palash Das	3	30,653	28,614
Dum Dum Uttar	GEN	AITC	Chandrima Bhattacharya	1	95,465	28,499
Dum Dum Uttar	GEN	BJP	Dr. Archana Majumdar	2	66,966	21,238
Dum Dum Uttar	GEN	CPM	Tanmoy Bhattacharya	3	45,728	43,617
Gaighata	SC	BJP	Subrata Thakur	1	100,808	9,578
Gaighata	SC	AITC	Narottam Biswas	2	91,230	76,392
Gaighata	SC	CPI	Kapil Krishna Thakur	3	14,838	13,312
Habra	GEN	AITC	Jyoti Priya Mallick	1	90,533	3,841
Habra	GEN	BJP	Biswajit Sinha	2	86,692	64,698
Habra	GEN	CPM	Rijinandan Biswas	3	21,994	20,704
Haroa	GEN	AITC	Islam Sk Nurul (Haji)	1	130,398	80,978
Haroa	GEN	RSSCMJP	Kutubuddin Fathe	2	49,420	10,914
Haroa	GEN	BJP	Rajendra Saha (Somu)	3	38,506	35,576
Hingalganj	SC	AITC	Debes Mandal	1	104,706	24,916
Hingalganj	SC	BJP	Nemai Das	2	79,790	73,782
Hingalganj	SC	CPI	Ranjan Kumar Mondal	3	6,008	4,272
Jagatdal	GEN	AITC	Somenath Shyam Ichini	1	87,030	18,364
Jagatdal	GEN	BJP	Arindam Bhattacharya	2	68,666	51,918
Jagatdal	GEN	AIFB	Nemai Saha	3	16,748	14,180
Kamarhati	GEN	AITC	Madan Mitra	1	73,845	35,408
Kamarhati	GEN	BJP	Anindya Banerjee	2	38,437	10,127
Kamarhati	GEN	CPM	Sayandeep Mitra	3	28,310	26,757

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Khurdaha	GEN	AITC	Kajal Sinha	1	89,807	28,140
Khurdaha	GEN	BJP	Silbhadra Datta	2	61,667	34,751
Khurdaha	GEN	CPM	Debajyoti Das (Subho)	3	26,916	24,501
Madhyamgram	GEN	AITC	Rathin Ghosh	1	112,741	48,126
Madhyamgram	GEN	BJP	Rajasree Rajbanshi	2	64,615	17,867
Madhyamgram	GEN	RSSCMJP	Biswajit Maity	3	46,748	43,596
Minakhan	SC	AITC	Usha Rani Mondal	1	109,818	55,830
Minakhan	SC	BJP	Jayanta Mondal	2	53,988	9,382
Minakhan	SC	CPM	Pradyut Roy	3	44,606	40,666
Naihati	GEN	AITC	Partha Bhowmick	1	77,753	18,855
Naihati	GEN	BJP	Phalguni Patra	2	58,898	43,073
Naihati	GEN	CPM	Indrani Kundu Mukherjee	3	15,825	14,124
Noapara	GEN	AITC	Manju Basu	1	94,203	26,710
Noapara	GEN	BJP	Sunil Singh	2	67,493	43,991
Noapara	GEN	INC	Subhankar Sarkar	3	23,502	20,616
Panihati	GEN	AITC	Nirmal Ghosh	1	86,495	25,177
Panihati	GEN	BJP	Sanmoy Bandyopadhyay	2	61,318	40,149
Panihati	GEN	INC	Tapas Majumder	3	21,169	18,835
Rajarhat Gopalpur	GEN	AITC	Aditi Munshi	1	87,650	25,296
Rajarhat Gopalpur	GEN	BJP	Samik Bhattacharya	2	62,354	37,843
Rajarhat Gopalpur	GEN	CPM	Subhajit Dasgupta	3	24,511	22,253
Rajarhat New Town	GEN	AITC	Tapash Chatterjee	1	127,374	56,432
Rajarhat New Town	GEN	BJP	Bhaskar Roy	2	70,942	39,399
Rajarhat New Town	GEN	CPM	Saptarshi Deb	3	31,543	29,511
Sandeshkhali	ST	AITC	Sukumar Mahata	1	112,450	39,685
Sandeshkhali	ST	BJP	Dr. Bhaskar Sardar	2	72,765	58,378
Sandeshkhali	ST	RSSCMJP	Barun Mahato	3	14,387	11,931
Swarupnagar	SC	AITC	Bina Mondal	1	99,784	34,800
Swarupnagar	SC	BJP	Brindaban Sarkar	2	64,984	21,702
Swarupnagar	SC	CPM	Biswajit Mandal	3	43,282	42,026

Annex 15: Paschim Medinipur District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Binpur	ST	AITC	Debnath Hansda	1	100,277	39,494
Binpur	ST	BJP	Palan Saren	2	60,783	52,430
Binpur	ST	CPM	Dibakar Hansda	3	8,353	2,035
Chandrakona	SC	AITC	Arup Dhara	1	121,846	11,281
Chandrakona	SC	BJP	Sibaram Das	2	110,565	99,764
Chandrakona	SC	RSSCMJP	Gouranga Das	3	10,801	7,895
Dantan	GEN	AITC	Bikram Chandra Pradhan	1	95,209	623
Dantan	GEN	BJP	Saktipada Nayak	2	94,586	88,934
Dantan	GEN	CPI	Sisir Kumar Patra	3	5,652	4,402
Daspur	GEN	AITC	Mamata Bhunia	1	114,753	26,842
Daspur	GEN	BJP	Prasanta Bera	2	87,911	70,866
Daspur	GEN	CPM	Dhruba Sekhar Mandal	3	17,045	15,658
Debra	GEN	AITC	Humayun Kabir	1	95,850	11,226
Debra	GEN	BJP	Bharati Ghosh	2	84,624	63,901
Debra	GEN	CPM	Prankrishna Mondal	3	20,723	19,214

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Garbeta	GEN	AITC	Uttara Singha (Hazra)	1	94,928	10,572
Garbeta	GEN	BJP	Madan Ruidas	2	84,356	61,314
Garbeta	GEN	CPM	Ghosh Kumar Tapan	3	23,042	20,323
Ghatal	SC	BJP	Sital Kapat	1	105,812	966
Ghatal	SC	AITC	Shankar Dolai	2	104,846	94,681
Ghatal	SC	CPM	Kamal Chandra Dolui	3	10,165	8,157
Gopiballavpur	GEN	AITC	Dr. Khagendra Nath Mahata	1	104,115	23,768
Gopiballavpur	GEN	BJP	Sanjit Mahata	2	80,347	74,528
Gopiballavpur	GEN	CPM	Prasanta Kumar Das	3	5,819	3,028
Jhargram	GEN	AITC	Birbaha Hansda	1	109,493	38,240
Jhargram	GEN	BJP	Sukhamay Satpathy (Jahar)	2	71,253	60,823
Jhargram	GEN	CPM	Madhuja Sen Roy	3	10,430	6,794
Keshiary	ST	AITC	Paresh Murmu	1	106,366	15,330
Keshiary	ST	BJP	Sonali Murmu Soren	2	91,036	81,766
Keshiary	ST	CPM	Dr. Pulin Bihari Baske	3	9,270	6,700
Keshpur	SC	AITC	Seuli Saha	1	116,992	20,720
Keshpur	SC	BJP	Pritish Ranjan Kuar	2	96,272	82,602
Keshpur	SC	CPM	Rameswar Doloi	3	13,670	10,372
Kharagpur	GEN	AITC	Dinen Roy	1	109,727	36,230
Kharagpur	GEN	BJP	Tapan Bhuya	2	73,497	62,252
Kharagpur	GEN	CPM	Syed Saddam Ali	3	11,245	8,931
Kharagpur Sadar	GEN	BJP	Hiranmoy Chattopadhyaya	1	79,607	3,771
Kharagpur Sadar	GEN	AITC	Pradip Sarkar	2	75,836	65,045
Kharagpur Sadar	GEN	INC	Reeta Sharma	3	10,791	8,148
Medinipur	GEN	AITC	June Maliah	1	121,175	24,397
Medinipur	GEN	BJP	Samit Kumar Dash	2	96,778	83,794
Medinipur	GEN	CPI	Tarun Kumar Ghosh	3	12,984	9,056
Narayangarh	GEN	AITC	Atta Surja Kanta	1	100,894	2,416
Narayangarh	GEN	BJP	Rama Prasad Giri	2	98,478	85,249
Narayangarh	GEN	CPM	Tapas Sinha	3	13,229	10,396
Nayagram	ST	AITC	Dulal Murmu	1	100,903	22,754
Nayagram	ST	BJP	Bakul Murmu	2	78,149	72,286
Nayagram	ST	CPM	Haripada Saren	3	5,863	2,777
Pingla	GEN	AITC	Ajit Maity	1	112,435	6,656
Pingla	GEN	BJP	Antara Bhattacharyya	2	105,779	98,676
Pingla	GEN	INC	Samir Roy	3	7,103	5,030
Sabang	GEN	AITC	Manas Ranjan Bhunia	1	112,098	9,864
Sabang	GEN	BJP	Amulya Maity	2	102,234	84,791
Sabang	GEN	INC	Chiranjib Bhowmik	3	17,443	15,909
Salboni	GEN	AITC	Srikanta Mahata	1	126,020	32,644
Salboni	GEN	BJP	Rajib Kundu	2	93,376	73,517
Salboni	GEN	CPM	Ghosh Susanta	3	19,859	17,216

Annex 16: Purba Medinipur District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Bhagabanpur	GEN	BJP	Rabindranath Maity	1	121,480	27,549
Bhagabanpur	GEN	AITC	Ardhendu Maity	2	93,931	88,657
Bhagabanpur	GEN	INC	Shiu Maiti	3	5,274	4,255
Chandipur	GEN	AITC	Soham Chakraborty	1	109,770	13,472
Chandipur	GEN	BJP	Pulak Kanti Guria	2	96,298	86,461
Chandipur	GEN	CPM	Ashis Kumar Guchhait	3	9,837	8,472
Egra	GEN	AITC	Tarun Kumar Maity	1	125,763	18,491
Egra	GEN	BJP	Arup Dash	2	107,272	102,186
Egra	GEN	INC	Manas K. Karmahapatra	3	5,086	3,693
Haldia	SC	BJP	Tapasi Mondal	1	104,126	15,008
Haldia	SC	AITC	Swapan Naskar	2	89,118	66,430
Haldia	SC	CPM	Kar Paik Manika	3	22,688	20,766
Kanthi Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Arup Kumar Das	1	98,477	10,293
Kanthi Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Jyotirmoy Kar	2	88,184	82,170
Kanthi Dakshin	GEN	CPI	Anurup Panda	3	6,014	4,878
Kanthi Uttar	GEN	BJP	Sumita Sinha	1	113,524	9,330
Kanthi Uttar	GEN	AITC	Tarun Kumar Jana	2	104,194	97,690
Kanthi Uttar	GEN	CPM	Sutanu Maity	3	6,504	5,012
Khejuri	SC	BJP	Santanu Pramanik	1	110,407	17,965
Khejuri	SC	AITC	Partha Pratim Das	2	92,442	84,630
Khejuri	SC	CPM	Himangshu Das	3	7,812	6,676
Mahisadal	GEN	AITC	Tilak Kumar Chakraborty	1	101,986	2,386
Mahisadal	GEN	BJP	Biswanath Banerjee	2	99,600	85,804
Mahisadal	GEN	RSSCMJP	Bikram Chatterjee	3	13,796	12,031
Moyna	GEN	BJP	Ashoke Dinda	1	108,109	1,260
Moyna	GEN	AITC	Sangram Kumar Dolai	2	106,849	101,741
Moyna	GEN	INC	Manik Bhaumik	3	5,108	3,434
Nandakumar	GEN	AITC	Sukumar De	1	108,181	5,406
Nandakumar	GEN	BJP	Adhikary Nilanjan	2	102,775	89,993
Nandakumar	GEN	CPM	Karuna Sankar Bhowmik	3	12,782	11,309
Nandigram	GEN	BJP	Adhikari Suvendu	1	110,764	1,956
Nandigram	GEN	AITC	Mamata Banerjee	2	108,808	102,541
Nandigram	GEN	CPM	Minakshi Mukherjee	3	6,267	5,177
Panskura Paschim	GEN	AITC	Phiroja Bibi	1	111,705	8,889
Panskura Paschim	GEN	BJP	Sintu Senapati	2	102,816	87,692
Panskura Paschim	GEN	CPI	Chittaranjan Dasthakur	3	15,124	13,787
Panskura Purba	GEN	AITC	Biplab Roy Chowdhury	1	91,213	9,660
Panskura Purba	GEN	BJP	Debabrata Pattanayek	2	81,553	60,836
Panskura Purba	GEN	CPM	Ibrahim Ali Sk	3	20,717	19,259
Patashpur	GEN	AITC	Uttam Barik	1	105,299	9,994
Patashpur	GEN	BJP	Ambujaksha Mahanti	2	95,305	88,674
Patashpur	GEN	CPI	Saikat Giri	3	6,631	5,770
Ramnagar	GEN	AITC	Akhil Giri	1	112,622	12,517
Ramnagar	GEN	BJP	Swadesh Ranjan Nayak	2	100,105	93,354
Ramnagar	GEN	CPM	Sabyasachi Jana	3	6,751	5,518
Tamluk	GEN	AITC	Saumen K. Mahapatra	1	108,243	793
Tamluk	GEN	BJP	Hare Krishna Bera	2	107,450	92,732
Tamluk	GEN	CPI	Goutam Panda	3	14,718	11,962

Annex 17: Purulia District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Baghmundi	GEN	AITC	Sushanta Mahato	1	75,905	13,969
Baghmundi	GEN	AJSUP	Ashutosh Mahato	2	61,936	10,890
Baghmundi	GEN	INC	Nepal Chandra Mahato	3	51,046	39,204
Balarampur	GEN	BJP	Baneswar Mahato	1	89,521	423
Balarampur	GEN	AITC	Shantiram Mahato	2	89,098	80,203
Balarampur	GEN	INC	Uttam Kumar Bandyopadhyay	3	8,895	6,454
Bandwan	ST	AITC	Rajib Lochan Saren	1	113,337	18,831
Bandwan	ST	BJP	Parcy Murmu	2	94,506	72,302
Bandwan	ST	CPM	Besra Susanta Kumar	3	22,204	17,137
Joypur	GEN	BJP	Nara Hari Mahato	1	74,380	12,200
Joypur	GEN	INC	Phanibhushan Kumar	2	62,180	26,751
Joypur	GEN	IND	Dibyajoti Singh Deo	3	35,429	16,016
Kashipur	GEN	BJP	Kamalakanta Hansda	1	92,938	7,387
Kashipur	GEN	AITC	Swapan Kumar Beltharia	2	85,551	74,624
Kashipur	GEN	CPM	Mallika Mahata	3	10,927	8,526
Manbazar	ST	AITC	Sandhyarani Tudu	1	103,298	15,516
Manbazar	ST	BJP	Gouri Singh Sardar	2	87,782	70,933
Manbazar	ST	CPM	Yaminikanta Mandi	3	16,849	14,558
Para	SC	BJP	Nadiar Chand Bouri	1	87,347	4,007
Para	SC	AITC	Umapada Bauri	2	83,340	69,659
Para	SC	CPM	Swapan Kumar Bauri	3	13,681	10,024
Purulia	GEN	BJP	Sudip Kumar Mukherjee	1	89,733	7,018
Purulia	GEN	AITC	Sujoy Banerjee	2	82,715	57,719
Purulia	GEN	INC	Partha Pratim Banerjee	3	24,996	22,408
Raghunathpur	SC	BJP	Vivekananda Bauri	1	95,770	5,438
Raghunathpur	SC	AITC	Bouri Hazari	2	90,332	75,594
Raghunathpur	SC	CPM	Ganesh Bouri	3	14,738	10,909

Annex 18: South 24 Parganas District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

Constituency	Type	Party	Candidate	Position	Votes	Margin
Baruipur Paschim	GEN	AITC	Biman Banerjee	1	121,006	61,910
Baruipur Paschim	GEN	BJP	Debopam Chattopadhyaya (Babu)	2	59,096	33,457
Baruipur Paschim	GEN	CPM	Md Lahek Ali	3	25,639	23,870
Baruipur Purba	SC	AITC	Bivas Sardar (Vobo)	1	123,243	49,641
Baruipur Purba	SC	BJP	Chandan Mondal	2	73,602	52,135
Baruipur Purba	SC	CPM	Swapan Naskar	3	21,467	19,612
Basanti	SC	AITC	Shyamal Mondal	1	111,453	50,642
Basanti	SC	BJP	Ramesh Majhi	2	60,811	24,123
Basanti	SC	RSP	Subhas Naskar	3	36,688	34,781
Behala Paschim	GEN	AITC	Partha Chatterjee	1	114,778	50,884
Behala Paschim	GEN	BJP	Srabanti Chatterjee	2	63,894	16,385
Behala Paschim	GEN	CPM	Nihar Bhakta	3	47,509	45,076
Behala Purba	GEN	AITC	Ratna Chatterjee	1	110,968	37,428
Behala Purba	GEN	BJP	Payel Sarkar	2	73,540	43,368

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Behala Purba	GEN	CPM	Samita Har Chowdhury	3	30,172	27,337
Bhangore	GEN	RSSCMJP	Md. Nawsad Siddique	1	109,237	26,151
Bhangore	GEN	AITC	Karim Rezaul	2	83,086	44,360
Bhangore	GEN	BJP	Soumi Hati	3	38,726	33,796
Bishnupur(Sc)	SC	AITC	Dilip Mondal	1	136,509	58,832
Bishnupur(Sc)	SC	BJP	Agniswar Naskar	2	77,677	59,682
Bishnupur(Sc)	SC	CPM	Jhuma Kayal	3	17,995	15,286
Budge Budge	GEN	AITC	Ashok Kumar Deb	1	122,357	44,714
Budge Budge	GEN	BJP	Dr. Tarun Kumar Adak	2	77,643	66,834
Budge Budge	GEN	INC	Sk Mujibar Rahaman	3	10,809	8,074
Canning Paschim	SC	AITC	Pareesh Ram Das	1	111,059	35,243
Canning Paschim	SC	BJP	Arnab Roy	2	75,816	62,426
Canning Paschim	SC	IND	Meghnath Halder	3	13,390	1,482
Canning Purba	GEN	AITC	Saokat Molla	1	122,301	53,007
Canning Purba	GEN	RSSCMJP	Gazi Shahabuddin Siraji	2	69,294	34,791
Canning Purba	GEN	BJP	Kalipada Naskar	3	34,503	31,817
Diamond Harbour	GEN	AITC	Pannalal Halder	1	98,478	16,996
Diamond Harbour	GEN	BJP	Dipak Kumar Halder	2	81,482	42,763
Diamond Harbour	GEN	CPM	Pratik Ur Rahaman	3	38,719	37,134
Falta	GEN	AITC	Sankar Kumar Naskar	1	116,713	39,928
Falta	GEN	BJP	Bidhan Parui	2	76,785	69,316
Falta	GEN	INC	Abdur Razzak Molla	3	7,469	5,793
Gosaba	SC	AITC	Jayanta Naskar	1	105,723	23,709
Gosaba	SC	BJP	Barun Pramanik (Chitta)	2	82,014	77,143
Gosaba	SC	RSP	Anil Chandra Mondal	3	4,871	3,600
Jadavpur	GEN	AITC	Debabrata Majumdar (Malay)	1	98,100	38,869
Jadavpur	GEN	CPM	Dr. Sujan Chakraborty	2	59,231	6,092
Jadavpur	GEN	BJP	Rinku Naskar	3	53,139	50,409
Jaqynagar	SC	AITC	Biswanath Das	1	104,952	38,683
Jaqynagar	SC	BJP	Rabin Sardar	2	66,269	48,901
Jaqynagar	SC	CPM	Apurba Pramanik (Apu)	3	17,368	7,945
Kakdwip	GEN	AITC	Manturam Pakhira	1	114,493	25,302
Kakdwip	GEN	BJP	Dipankar Jana	2	89,191	76,957
Kakdwip	GEN	INC	Indranil Rout	3	12,234	10,604
Kasba	GEN	AITC	Ahmed Javed Khan	1	121,372	63,622
Kasba	GEN	BJP	Dr. Indranil Khan	2	57,750	18,570
Kasba	GEN	CPM	Shatarup Ghosh	3	39,180	36,704
Kulpi	GEN	AITC	Jogaranjan Halder	1	96,577	33,818
Kulpi	GEN	BJP	Pranab Kumar Mallik	2	62,759	32,798
Kulpi	GEN	RSSCMJP	Siraj Uddin Gazi	3	29,961	28,276
Kultali	SC	AITC	Ganesh Chandra Mondal	1	117,238	47,177
Kultali	SC	BJP	Mintu Halder	2	70,061	50,051
Kultali	SC	CPM	Ram Sankar Halder	3	20,010	4,704

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Magrahat Paschim	GEN	AITC	Gias Uddin Molla	1	97,006	46,941
Magrahat Paschim	GEN	BJP	Dhurjati Saha (Manas)	2	50,065	9,380
Magrahat Paschim	GEN	RSSCMJP	Maidul Islam Molla	3	40,685	38,399
Magrahat Purba	SC	AITC	Namita Saha	1	110,945	54,079
Magrahat Purba	SC	BJP	Chandan Kumar Naskar	2	56,866	23,044
Magrahat Purba	SC	CPM	Chandan Saha	3	33,822	32,342
Maheshkala	GEN	AITC	Dulal Chandra Das	1	124,008	57,949
Maheshkala	GEN	BJP	Umesh Das	2	66,059	40,783
Maheshkala	GEN	CPM	Pravat Chowdhury	3	25,276	23,227
Mandirbazar	SC	AITC	Joydeb Halder	1	95,834	23,492
Mandirbazar	SC	BJP	Dilip Kumar Jatua	2	72,342	46,945
Mandirbazar	SC	RSSCMJP	Sanchay Kumar Sarkar	3	25,397	23,575
Metiaburuz	GEN	AITC	Abdul Khaleque Molla	1	151,066	119,604
Metiaburuz	GEN	BJP	Ramjit Prasad	2	31,462	24,073
Metiaburuz	GEN	RSSCMJP	Nuruzaman Molla	3	7,389	4,381
Patharpratima	GEN	AITC	Samir Kumar Jana	1	120,181	22,134
Patharpratima	GEN	BJP	Asit Kumar Halder	2	98,047	87,865
Patharpratima	GEN	INC	Shukdeb Bera	3	10,182	8,518
Raidighi	GEN	AITC	Aloke Jaldata	1	115,707	35,568
Raidighi	GEN	BJP	Santanu Bapuli	2	80,139	43,208
Raidighi	GEN	CPM	Kanti Ganguly	3	36,931	34,069
Sagar	GEN	AITC	Bankim Chandra Hazra	1	129,000	29,846
Sagar	GEN	BJP	Kamila Bikash	2	99,154	90,058
Sagar	GEN	CPM	Sk Muklesur Rahaman	3	9,096	8,071
Satgachia	GEN	AITC	Mohan Chandra Naskar	1	118,635	23,318
Satgachia	GEN	BJP	Chandan Pal	2	95,317	79,097
Satgachia	GEN	CPM	Goutam Pal	3	16,220	14,595
Sonarpur Dakshin	GEN	AITC	Arundhuti Maitra (Lovely)	1	109,222	26,181
Sonarpur Dakshin	GEN	BJP	Anjana Basu	2	83,041	51,263
Sonarpur Dakshin	GEN	CPI	Shuvam Banerjee	3	31,778	29,228
Sonarpur Uttar	GEN	AITC	Firdousi Begum	1	119,957	36,090
Sonarpur Uttar	GEN	BJP	Ranjan Baidya	2	83,867	54,467
Sonarpur Uttar	GEN	CPM	Monalisa Sinha	3	29,400	27,286
Tollygunj	GEN	AITC	Aroop Biswas	1	101,440	50,080
Tollygunj	GEN	BJP	Babul Supriyo	2	51,360	10,763
Tollygunj	GEN	CPM	Debdut Ghosh	3	40,597	38,287

Annex 19: Uttar Dinajpur District Election Results: Top 3 Candidates by Votes in Each Constituency

<i>Constituency</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Party</i>	<i>Candidate</i>	<i>Position</i>	<i>Votes</i>	<i>Margin</i>
Chakulia	GEN	AITC	Azad Minhajul Arfin	1	86,311	33,837
Chakulia	GEN	BJP	Sachin Prasad	2	52,474	23,770
Chakulia	GEN	AIFB	Ali Imran Ramz	3	28,704	25,979
Chopra	GEN	AITC	Hamidul Rahaman	1	124,923	64,905
Chopra	GEN	BJP	Md. Shahin Akhter	2	60,018	47,739
Chopra	GEN	CPM	Anwarul Haque	3	12,279	9,113
Goalpokhar	GEN	AITC	Md. Ghulam Rabbani	1	105,649	73,514
Goalpokhar	GEN	BJP	Md. Ghulam Sarwar	2	32,135	12,744
Goalpokhar	GEN	INC	Masood Md. Naseem Ahsen	3	19,391	17,375
Hemtabad	SC	AITC	Satyajit Barman	1	116,425	27,215
Hemtabad	SC	BJP	Chandima Roy	2	89,210	79,757
Hemtabad	SC	CPM	Bhupen Barman	3	9,453	7,293
Islampur	GEN	AITC	Abdul Karim Chowdhary	1	100,131	37,440
Islampur	GEN	BJP	Saumyaroop Mandal	2	62,691	59,230
Islampur	GEN	INC	Sadiqul Islam	3	3,461	1,485
Itahar	GEN	AITC	Mosaraf Hussen	1	114,645	43,975
Itahar	GEN	BJP	Amit Kumar Kundu	2	70,670	65,762
Itahar	GEN	CPI	Srikumar Mukherjee	3	4,908	3,668
Kaliaganj	SC	BJP	Soumen Roy	1	116,768	21,820
Kaliaganj	SC	AITC	Tapan Deb Singha	2	94,948	78,178
Kaliaganj	SC	INC	Pravash Sarkar	3	16,770	12,766
Karandighi	GEN	AITC	Goutam Paul	1	116,594	36,626
Karandighi	GEN	BJP	Subhas Chandra Sinha S/O: Haranarayan Sinha	2	79,968	70,822
Karandighi	GEN	AIFB	Md. Hafizul Iqbal	3	9,146	6,697
Raiganj	GEN	BJP	Krishna Kalyani	1	79,775	20,748
Raiganj	GEN	AITC	Agarwal Kanaia Lal	2	59,027	41,829
Raiganj	GEN	INC	Mohit Sengupta	3	17,198	14,730

AUTHOR' DECLARATIONS AND ESSENTIAL ETHICAL COMPLIANCES

Author' Contributions (in accordance with ICMJE criteria for authorship)

This article is 100% contributed by the sole author. She conceived and designed the research or analysis, collected the data, contributed to data analysis & interpretation, wrote the article, performed critical revision of the article/paper, edited the article, and supervised and administered the field work.

Funding

No funding was available for the research conducted for and writing of this paper.

Research involving human bodies (Helsinki Declaration)

Has this research used human subjects for experimentation? No

Research involving animals (ARRIVE Checklist)

Has this research involved animal subjects for experimentation? No

Research involving Plants

No plant was used to conduct this research.

Research on Indigenous Peoples and/or Traditional Knowledge

Has this research involved Indigenous Peoples as participants or respondents? No

(Optional) PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)

Have authors complied with PRISMA standards? No

Competing Interests/Conflict of Interest

Author has no competing financial, professional, or personal interests from other parties or in publishing this manuscript.

RIGHTS AND PERMISSIONS

Open Access. This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.